

6G MULTiband Wireless and Optical Signalling for Integrated
CommunicAtions, Sensing and Localisation

D2.1 '6G-MUSICAL project requirements, use cases, PoCs outline, KPIs and KVIs'

Deliverable number:	D2.1
Deliverable nature:	Standard
Dissemination level:	Public
Work Package(s):	WP2
Version:	V1.0
Date:	31 st of December 2024

Executive summary

6G-MUSICAL, in the frame of the European Commission's (EC) SNS (Smart Network Services) Joint Undertaking, is a ground-breaking project that merges radio sensing and communication technologies to create new paradigms in RF communication. It aims to equip edge infrastructure nodes of 6G with integrated RF/radar-based radio-sensing elements that co-work with communication components. This enables localization, object tracking and 3D imaging, with cm-level precision and resolution. As such, the project will investigate new spectrally and energy-efficient system architectures and signals to facilitate high-rate communication across multi-frequency bands integrated with accurate sensing and localisation.

Compared to other joint communication and sensing research, 6G-MUSICAL stands out in two ways. First, it considers sensing for both connected and non-connected objects, which is important given the trend towards connecting everything. Second, it addresses the synchronization of edge nodes, which is critical to achieving extreme levels of accuracy and resolution. The project will combine optical and electronic technologies to generate precise and stable references, enabling a network of smart cooperative multi-static radars within future 6G, bringing new services, high-accuracy localisation and high-resolution 3D object reconstruction.

In the wireless domain, the project will define new waveforms suitable for radio-sensing and communications, exploit compressive sensing techniques and define cooperative multimode sensing and localisation algorithms. In the network domain, the focus will be on procedures for synchronisation/calibration among edge nodes and on compression techniques to enable low-overhead transport to a data fusion centre of the collected information. The optical/electrical technology will develop and distribute the reference signals and will create novel antennas to address 6G requirements. Machine learning will be used to optimise the system and services jointly. Key technologies will be demonstrated in labs to meet a stringent set of predefined KPIs.

6G-MUSICAL's Work Package 2 (WP2), "Use Cases, Requirements, Architecture and Sustainability," establishes the project framework, encompassing scenarios, use cases, system requirements, and high-level architecture. The results of this WP will serve as guidelines and primary inputs for technology development in other WPs.

WP2 will mainly contribute to two 6G-MUSICAL overarching objectives, such as objective 1 (i.e., examine the requirements of users in the intended application domains and produce a comprehensive overview of the infrastructure requirements for the target Proof of Concepts (PoCs) and objective 6 (i.e., facilitate the architecture of the 6G and co-design process, involving all stakeholders, to identify the most appropriate technical components and necessary improvements).

This deliverable, D2.1, constitutes the first actual deliverable of WP2. It's based on the M3 internal report. It presents relevant information for use cases, requirements analysis for PoC refinement, and definition of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and Key Value Indicators (KVIs), including evaluation methodology.

WP2 will play a crucial role in the 6G-MUSICAL project by providing the requirements to serve as guidelines and primary inputs for technology development in other WPs. In the second part of WP2, inputs from technical WPs will be received to perform a technology analysis regarding impact and sustainability. Furthermore, WP2 will collaborate with WP6 "Integration and Validation" by providing use case definitions, requirements, and architecture that will be used in the PoCs activities.

Document Information

Project Number	Horizon Europe - 101139176	Acronym	6G-MUSICAL
Full Title	6G MULTiband Wireless and Optical Signalling for Integrated CommunicAtions, Sensing and Localisation		
Project URL	www.6gmusical.eu		
Document URL			
EU Project Officer	Cristina CULLELL MARCH		

Date of Delivery	Contractual	31/12/2024 (M12)	Actual	17/01/2025 (M13)
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Issue Date	Rev. No.	Change
31/08/2024	V0.1	ToC ready
30/09/2024	V0.2	Initial contributions and nomination of reviewers
22/11/2024	V0.3	Final contributions
26/11/2024	V0.4	First full draft to TM & PC
03/12/2024	V0.5	Feedback from WPL 3-6
07/12/2024	V0.6	Comments addressed, version to TM & PC
14/12/2024	V0.7	Feedback to DE by TM & PC
30/12/2024	V0.8	Tentative final version consolidated
15/01/2025	V0.9	Final version
17/01/2025	V1.0	Submitted version

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Abbreviations

Acronym	Definition
3D	Three dimensional
3GPP	3rd Generation Partnership Project
ADPCM	Adaptive Differential Pulse-Code Modulation
AGV	Automated Guided Vehicle
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AoA	Angle of Arrival
AP	Access Point
BRSRP	Beam-RSRP
BS	Base Station
CNN	Convolutional Neural Network
COTS	Commercial Off the Shelf
CSI	Channel State Information
DL	Downlink
DNN	Domain Name Network
EC	European Commission
EDP	Energy of Direct Path
FPGA	Field-programable gate array
GA	Grant Agreement
GPS	Global Positioning System
ISAC	Integrated Sensing and Communications
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
KVIs	Key Value Indicators
LOS	Line-of-Sight
LSTM	Long Short-Term Memory
MIMO	Multiple Input Multiple Output
ML	Machine Learning
NIC	Network Interface Card
NLOS	Non-Line-of-Sight
NR	New Radio
OFDM	Orthogonal frequency-division multiplexing
PoC	Proof of Concept
PRS	Positioning Reference Signal
RAN	Radio Access Network
RCS	Radio Communication System
RDF	Radio Direction Finders
RSRP	Reference Signal Received Power
RSSI	Received Signal Strength Indicator
RTT	Round Trip Time
SINR	Signal to Interference and Noise Ratio
SNS	Smart Networks and Services
SRS	Sounding Reference Signals
TDOA	Time Difference of Arrival
ToA	Time of Arrival

TRP	Transmit Receive Point
UAV	Unmanned Aerial Vehicle
UE	User Equipment
UL	Uplink
WP	Work Package
XR	Extended Reality

1 Introduction

The Work Package (WP) 2 “Use Cases, Requirements, Architecture and Sustainability” of the 6G-MUSICAL project focuses on requirements and use cases definition for implementing a comprehensive set of innovative communication, localisation and sensing technologies. The 6G-MUSICAL use cases will be based on various solutions such as positioning, localisation of connected and unconnected objects, contact-free imaging and spectroscopy for health applications, hyperlocal weather sensing, XR applications and smart home applications covering the relevant domains such as health, transportation and smart home and cities.

Deliverable D2.1 represents the first deliverable of WP2, aiming to detail the selection of enabling technologies and the outline definition of the testing scenarios for WP6 “Integration and Validation”. The scenarios will focus on the two trends of the project: communications and radio-sensing. Concerning the former, D2.1 aligns with the main ongoing trends, namely checking activities in 3GPP and European projects, as they are expected to be evolutive. There is much more openness for radio-sensing as this is a novel component that does not exist in any of the five “5” Gs. D2.1 collects the existing information in the literature and checks the current worldwide initiatives to be critically analysed under the leadership of the operator and big manufacturer present in the consortium. The deliverable also selects typical use cases, leading to the description of scenarios for technical development.

D2.1 also presents the relevant KPIs and KQIs for communication and sensing. The project approach considers that for communication, KPIs and KQIs will reflect ongoing developments in Europe and worldwide, while additional research is needed for the radio-sensing component. The methodology for defining requirements is based on a top-down approach.

- First, different ecosystems are identified, and their main characteristics are described, leading to a requirements matrix.
- Second, the types of equipment in these ecosystems are identified, including different wireless technologies, frequencies, and power.
- Third, commonalities between the different ecosystems are identified to establish a baseline architecture that can eventually be configured to fit specific environments.

1.1 Deliverable overview

The main sections of the D2.1 are described below.

Section 2 describes the deliverable's radio, localisation, and definitions of sensing terms.

Section 3 presents the 3GPP and 5G-PPP standardisation activities related to sensing and analysis technologies, such as 5G-enabled and radar-based localisation and sensing technologies. The section also details the possibility of using AI/ML algorithms that improve hardware-based sensing technologies.

Section 4 indicates the technical requirements and evaluation methodology for each use case. It reports the technical requirements (e.g., throughput, latency, accuracy, etc.) that the platforms and network solutions should fulfil (i.e., input to WP6) to implement the use case. It describes the relevant KPIs and KQIs and proposes a preliminary mapping of the requirements and performance figures into radio parameters.

Section 5 describes potential PoCs such as cooperative communication and multi-static sensing based on the OFDM waveform, generation and robust distribution of references to synchronise the network, and usage of liquid crystal technology from Antenna to RAN.

Section 6 presents the selection of use cases based on PoCs requirements, implementation aspects such as architecture based on the technologies to be developed within WP3/4/5 and provides expectations towards the relevant KPIs and KVI.

Section 7 provides the interworking methodology between project WPs.

Finally, Section 8, the conclusions, summarizes the main outcomes of the document and reports the next steps related to WP2 activities.

2 Definitions

This section outlines the definitions of the main terms involving radio and localisation, which will be used in future 6G Integrated Sensing and Communications (ISAC) applications and technologies.

2.1 Radio Terms Definitions

Understanding the general terminology used for radio systems is crucial to understanding the rest of this report. This section defines key terms of radio systems, covering radar and communications systems.

- Interference occurs when unwanted signals disrupt the transmission or reception of desired signals. Various sources, such as competing radio transmissions, electromagnetic noise, or physical obstructions can cause it.
- Multiple Access refers to the ability of multiple users or communication devices to share the same communication channel simultaneously. It enables efficient utilisation of bandwidth and spectrum resources, allowing multiple users to communicate without significant interference.
- Duplexing allows bidirectional communication over a single communication channel, enabling simultaneous transmission and reception. Two standard methods of duplexing are:
 - Time-division duplexing: A method that allows duplex communication links where the allocation of different time slots separates transmission and reception in the same frequency band.
 - Frequency-division duplexing: A method that simultaneously enables duplex communication links by allocating different frequency bands for transmission and reception.
- Line of Sight (LOS) in communications or radar refers to a scenario where there is no obstruction between transmitter-receiver (communications) or between transmitter-target (radar), i.e., we have a direct path or vision from Tx to Rx (Tx to target).
- Non-Line of Sight (NLOS) scenarios refer to a scenario where there are obstructions between transmitter-receiver (communications) or between transmitter-target (radar), i.e., we do not have a direct path or vision from Tx to Rx (Tx to target). This typically occurs in urban environments where the connection between the UE and the BS/objects is obstructed.
- Angle of Departure (AoD) characterises the direction in which electromagnetic waves are emitted from a transmitting antenna, measured with respect to the boresight angle. This parameter is fundamental for optimising wireless communication systems' beamforming and spatial signal processing.
- Angle of Arrival (AoA) characterises the direction of received electromagnetic waves relative to the boresight angle at a multi-antenna receiver. It provides useful insight into the spatial origin of electromagnetic signals, which is essential for applications like wireless communications, radar, and localisation systems.
- Multipath Propagation occurs when radio signals reflect off various surfaces, such as buildings, vehicles, or other objects. As a result, multiple copies of the same signal, each having reflected off different surfaces, arrive at the receiver at varying time intervals.

2.2 Localisation and Sensing Terms Definitions

Localization and sensing play pivotal roles in various applications, including radar systems, where precise detection and tracking are essential. This section elucidates key terms fundamental to understanding the principles and capabilities of localization and sensing technologies.

- Monostatic refers to the radar configuration where the transmitter and receiver are collocated, sharing the same antenna for both transmission and reception. This configuration simplifies system design but may limit detection range.
- Bi-static refers to radar configuration where the transmitter and receiver are located separately, with distinct antennas for transmission and reception. This setup offers advantages such as increased detection range and reduced vulnerability to jamming.
- Multi-static radar system comprises multiple transmitters and receivers distributed across different locations, enabling enhanced coverage, improved detection capabilities, and resilience to interference and jamming.
- Quasi-monostatic refers to an arrangement where the transmitter and receiver antennas are separated but still located in the same premises. This can be also termed bistatic but with a very small space separation between transmitter and receiver.
- MIMO radar employs multiple antennas for both transmission and reception, utilizing spatial diversity to enhance detection, localization, and tracking performance.
- Probability of detection is the probability of detecting a target given it is present. The probability of misdetection is $1 - \text{probability of detection}$.
- Probability of false alarm denotes the likelihood of erroneously detecting a target or event when none is present, often influenced by noise, clutter, or system errors.
- Resolution characterizes the ability of a radar system to distinguish between closely spaced targets or features in its observation area, typically determined by factors such as antenna beamwidth and signal processing techniques.
- Accuracy reflects the degree of conformity between the measured parameters (e.g., position, velocity) provided by a radar system and their true values, influencing the reliability and precision of target tracking and localisation.
- Tracking capacity denotes the maximum number of targets that a radar system can simultaneously detect, track, and maintain accurate positional information for, within its operational capabilities.
- Radar-cross section (RCS) quantifies the reflectivity of a target to radar signals, indicating the strength of the radar echo returned by the target relative to its size and orientation. A larger RCS indicates a more detectable target.
- Clutter refers to unwanted radar returns caused by non-target objects or environmental conditions, such as terrain features, precipitation, and man-made structures, which can obscure or degrade the detection of actual targets.

3 Communications and sensing state-of-the-art review

This section provides a high-level view of the main standardisation activities in the context of 5G/B5G localisation services, the existing state-of-the-art technologies for implementing cellular localisation, and the AI/ML-based algorithms used to enhance the accuracy of classical solutions.

3.1 3GPP, 5G-PPP Standardisation Activities

The integration of sensing and communication has become a timely topic in the past years and is expected to become a new capability of future wireless systems. Extensive academic research has been conducted in the last 10 years in important research areas, ranging from waveform design, precoding/receiver design, fundamental information theoretical limits, network architectures, and framed design for ISAC. More recently, prominent standardization bodies like 3GPP and ETSI already initiated efforts to incorporate sensing into their specifications.

Early pre-standardization studies are being conducted by the Service & System Aspects (SA) Technical Specification Group (TSG) within 3GPP. As part of Rel. 19, TR 22.837 [1] investigates the potential of integrated sensing and communication technology for enabling new services and use cases for various industries. More specifically, there are described a wide range of use cases covering a wide range of applications like public safety, object and intruder detection for smart homes, highways, and sensitive areas, weather monitoring, etc. The described use cases focus on 5G and, in some cases, may include interoperability with other types of sensors outside the cellular network like radar or cameras. Also, the Rel. 19 TS22.137 [2] outlines the functional and performance criteria for sensing services as part of 5G, incorporating both mono-static and bi-static configurations. Functionally, it addresses configuration and authorisation, network exposure, security and privacy, and charging. Various key performance indicators (KPI) are defined, including accuracy of positioning/velocity estimate, confidence level, sensing resolution, refreshing rate, and false alarm/miss detection probabilities. Additionally, use cases are categorised into three scenarios: object detection and tracking, environment monitoring, and motion monitoring.

ETSI has also started pre-standardization efforts through its Industry Specification Group (ISG), which concentrates on ISAC. Under the ISG ISAC work programme, ETSI conducts informative studies on 6G use cases and deployment scenarios, channel modelling, system, and Radio Access Network (RAN) architectures and addresses security, privacy, trustworthiness, and sustainability aspects. The pre-standardization efforts of ETSI's ISG ISAC encompass various key areas, including developing a roadmap for prioritised ISAC 6G use cases and sensing types, aiming to cover advanced use cases not addressed in current standards. Moreover, advanced radio channel models are being devised to overcome existing limitations and are validated through extensive measurement campaigns. Additionally, specifications for KPIs and evaluation methodologies are being formulated. Architectural changes at the System and Radio Access Network levels are under scrutiny to accommodate ISAC in 6G, considering aspects such as integration levels, deployment modes, and the choice of radio access technologies. Importantly, mechanisms are being studied to ensure that security and privacy requirements are met within the ISAC framework. Furthermore, the potential impact of widespread ISAC deployment on United Nations (UN) sustainability goals is being thoroughly examined.

3.2 5G-enabled Localisation and Sensing Technologies

Classical approaches to precise positioning and localisation within 5G networks predominantly utilise

geometric principles, specifically trilateration [3] and triangulation [4] (Figure 1), leveraging the following parameters:

1. **Time of Arrival (ToA)** and **Time Difference of Arrival (TdoA)** parameters measure the time it takes for a signal to travel from the UE to the BS or vice versa. By calculating the ToA between different BSs and UEs and knowing the speed of light as the radio signal's propagation speed, we can estimate the distance between multiple BSs and UEs. This information enables us to position the user accurately using the trilateration method as presented in Figure 1 a);
2. **Angle of Arrival (AoA)** parameter leverages the capabilities of directional antennas and antenna arrays in 5G networks, characterised by their beamforming transmission techniques. This setup facilitates the precise determination of the angle at which a signal from the UE reaches the BS. By estimating the AoA between the UE and multiple BSs, it is possible to accurately locate the UE using the triangulation method as presented in Figure 1 b);
3. **Received Signal Strength Indicator (RSSI)** is a parameter employed across various radio communication systems to assess the connection quality between the UE and the BS. It operates on the principle that radio signals attenuate as they travel over a distance. By measuring the RSSI values between the UE and multiple BSs and comparing these measurements to expected values derived from a radio propagation model, the distance between the UE and the BSs can be estimated. Subsequently, the final location and positioning of the UE are determined through the trilateration process.
4. **Cell-ID-based positioning** represents one of the most basic methods within the scope of location services, yet it is also the method most prone to introducing significant positioning errors. This approach relies on the relatively small size of cells in 5G communications, often referred to as pico-cells. By identifying the location of a cell through its Cell-ID, UE can be approximately positioned within the range of that specific cell.

Figure 1 - a) UE positioning via trilateration method b) UE positioning via triangulation method

While these traditional methods of location and positioning offer satisfactory outcomes in numerous scenarios, being generalisable due to the geometrical approach involved, they are accompanied by several challenges, particularly within the context of 5G networks. These challenges predominantly originate from the complexities of radio signal propagation in the dense and clustered urban environments characteristic of 5G networks. Such conditions can substantially impact the precision of location and positioning services. The primary challenges associated with traditional location and positioning techniques in 5G networks include:

1. **Multipath Propagation:** This phenomenon occurs when radio signals transmitted by the UE to the BS reflect off various surfaces, such as buildings, vehicles, or other objects. As a result, multiple copies of the same signal, each having reflected off different surfaces, arrive at the BS at varying time intervals. This situation complicates the accurate determination of ToA and TDoA, leading to significant uncertainties regarding the actual signal propagation path and,

consequently, the precise distance between the UE and the BS;

2. **Non-Line of Sight (NLOS) Scenarios:** Urban environments, common in 5G networks, often present situations where the connection between the UE and the BS does not occur in a LOS manner. This lack of direct visibility introduces challenges in accurately estimating the AoA and ToA parameters, making it difficult to achieve estimates that closely approximate the real values;
3. **Signal Attenuation and Interference:** When employing trilateration for positioning based on RSSI measurements, the estimation of radio signal attenuation through propagation models typically considers only the signal attenuation over distance, neglecting potential interference. This oversight can result in inaccurate distance estimations from RSSI measurements, subsequently leading to errors in the positioning of the UE;
4. **Need for Multiple Base Stations:** The effectiveness of triangulation and trilateration-based methods for positioning hinges on the availability of at least two to three BS. This requirement is essential to enhance the accuracy of positioning the UE. However, in certain scenarios, the required number of BS may not be readily available, posing a significant challenge to achieving increased positional accuracy.

3.3 Radar-based localisation and sensing technologies

Radar has been the traditional approach to detection, localisation, estimation and sensing. Unlike the 5G-based localisation approaches relying on communication signals and waveforms, radar signalling is specifically tailored to localisation and sensing, relying on good correlation and ambiguity function attributes. Joint range-angle detection allows single radars to localise targets without trilateration, as above. Key parameters include:

1. **Time of Arrival (ToA)** and **Time Difference of Arrival (Tdoa)** parameters measure the time it takes for a signal to travel from the radar to the target and back. One can estimate the target's range by calculating the ToA between different radars and targets. The signal bandwidth limits the resolution in the range;
2. **Angle of Arrival (AoA)** parameter can be estimated in multi-antenna (MIMO) radars. The multi-antenna setup facilitates the precise determination of the angle at which an echo from the target reaches the radar. By jointly estimating the ToA and AoA as shown in Figure 2, it is possible to split the space into range-angle bins and formulate a binary hypothesis test for each bin to determine if a target is present. The size of the antenna array limits the resolution in angle;
3. **Velocity** can be estimated by measuring the Doppler shift, the displacement of the perceived frequency at the radar receiver concerning the carrier frequency transmitted by the radar transmitter.
4. **Target classification** and **gesture recognition:** Micro-Doppler effects, that represent further Doppler shifts across the main shift of the target, can be used to determine the relative mobility of parts of the target, particularly useful in target classification and gesture recognition;
5. **Radar cross-section (RCS)** measures how detectable an object is by radar. A larger RCS indicates that an object is more easily detected. The factors that influence the RCS include the material with which the target is made, the size of the target relative to the wavelength of the illuminating radar signal, the angle at which the radar beam hits a particular portion of the target, and the shape of the target and its orientation. RCS can be used as a unique signature of a target; very useful in

distinguishing and associating data to targets in multi-target scenarios.

Figure 2 - Range-angle detection through binary hypothesis testing

While these traditional radar methods of location and positioning offer satisfactory outcomes in numerous scenarios, they are accompanied by several challenges, particularly within the context of 6G networks. These challenges predominantly originate from the radio signal propagation in the dense and cluttered urban environments, and the foreseen population of radars/sensors. Such conditions can substantially impact the precision of location and positioning services. The primary challenges associated with traditional location and positioning techniques in 6G networks include:

1. **Clutter:** The scatterers that exist in typical urban environments create multiple reflections and propagation paths, and the resulting echoes will create detection/estimation events that do not relate to the target of interest and are typically considered as interference/noise;
2. **Non-Line of Sight (NLOS) Scenarios:** Classical radar relies on the existence of a LOS link to the target. Urban environments, which are common in cellular networks, will present situations where the connection between the radar and target does not occur in a Line of Sight (LOS) manner. This lack of direct visibility introduces challenges in accurately estimating the AoA and ToA parameters, making it difficult to achieve estimates that closely approximate the real values;
3. **Interference:** When envisioning a perceptive cellular network with multiple radars operating in the scene, the different radar signals will interfere. This is a situation rarely occurring in radar only scenarios such as military or airborne aviation scenarios where typically one long-range, high-power radar operates with limited interference;
4. **Sensor fusion:** single-radar detection inevitable incurs uncertainty in the target detection/estimation/classification due to the above challenges. Fusing data from different radars allows an often-significant reduction in the uncertainty, but at the cost of significant signalling overheads. This represents a particular opportunity for ISAC networks where the existing cellular network backbone can be exploited for data fusion.

3.4 AI/ML algorithms that improve hardware-based sensing technologies

Recent advancements in the literature highlight various methods aimed at enhancing UE positioning and localisation within 5G networks, leveraging Machine Learning (ML) and Deep Learning (DL) algorithms. These algorithms are particularly good at learning from the nonlinear dynamics introduced by the challenges inherent in traditional UE positioning techniques. By using ML and DL techniques, it becomes feasible to achieve accurate localisation even in scenarios characterised by NLOS conditions, multipath fading, interference, or when only a single BS is available.

One of the most common methods for incorporating ML and DL algorithms into User UE positioning and localisation within 5G networks relies on location fingerprinting. This technique distinguishes itself primarily in the way measurements are captured and pre-processed. The objective is to generate the most discriminative features that can accurately distinguish between different locations. Through this approach, the unique "fingerprint" of a location comprised of various signal characteristics such as RSSI, AoA, ToA, is used to train ML and DL models. These models learn to recognise the patterns associated with each fingerprint, enabling them to accurately predict the location of the UE based on the signal features it observes, even in the complex and dynamic environments typical of 5G networks.

The positioning applications in 5G networks based on ML and DL algorithms can be split into two broad categories: indoor UE positioning and outdoor UE positioning. The mmWave 5G NR enabled radar applications are currently based on radar like processing without the implementation of ML and DL algorithms.

3.4.1 Indoor UE positioning enhancement using ML and DL algorithms

In [5] Fangy Yu et al., a novel approach utilising Deep Learning Residual Networks is proposed to mitigate UE positioning errors, particularly under challenging NLOS conditions in 5G communication networks for indoor deployment. The research introduces a system model where multiple BS are deployed indoors in a matrix configuration at set distances to facilitate precise positioning. The methodology for gathering data for UE positioning involves measuring the Channel Impulse Response (CIR) [6] and Reference Signal Received Power (RSRP) [7] from each BS to the UE in different locations of the room, creating a location fingerprint database that can be used to train the DL network. These measured values of CIR and RSRP are then compiled into a feature vector, which is used as the input for a four-layer residual Convolutional Neural Network (CNN). This network is specifically designed to estimate and output the X and Y coordinates of the UE, with each measurement comprising 256 samples. The study reveals that for CIR measurements, the most significant information is predominantly found in the first half of the sample indices. Given this insight, the authors implement a data truncation strategy to diminish computational complexity without substantially compromising accuracy. The residual CNN, leveraging both CIR and RSRP data, achieved a positioning accuracy of 0.28 m. When data truncation was applied, there was a slight decrease in accuracy to 0.35 m. Interestingly, when relying solely on CIR data, the system achieved a positioning accuracy of 0.47 m without data truncation and 0.4 m with it.

In [8] Quian et al., an enhanced variant of the DeepFi [9] neural network, is used for indoor positioning of UE utilising 5G New Radio Signals. Similar to other approaches found in the literature, their approach is based on location fingerprinting at predetermined reference points within an indoor setting. Each fingerprint captures Channel State Information (CSI) measurements, specifically focusing on ADCPM (Angle-Delay Channel Power Matrices), which considers the effects of multipath propagation and fading. The proposed method is split into two distinct phases: an initial offline training phase, where a four-layer DL network is trained with CSI measurements, and an online inference phase that processes real-time data CSI measurements. For real-time inference, the researchers propose the use of OFDM (Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiplexing) pilot subcarrier signals, aiming to minimise interference with the data transmission rates of the 5G network, ensuring integration of the UE positioning system with minimal interference to the 5G network. A notable improvement over the DeepFi architecture is the simplification of the network structure. DeepFi employs an ensemble of Autoencoders [10], each designed to a specific reference point within the room, while the proposed method utilises a singular network model. In this model, each reference point corresponds to a different output, simplifying the network's architecture. This approach generates a positioning

accuracy of 96% and a positioning error reduction of 65%, alongside maintaining a Signal-to-Interference-plus-Noise Ratio (SINR) of 88%. The positioning accuracy of this approach is presented as a percent due to the classification approach to the UE positioning task. Despite the high accuracy percent presented by the authors, the methodology faces several challenges. The positioning task is framed mainly as a classification problem centred around the distinct reference points, rather than a regression and location estimation problem. Consequently, the actual accuracy of the system heavily depends on the resolution of the reference points sampled. High-resolution sampling of reference points, while beneficial for accuracy, significantly increases the complexity of the DL network due to the necessity to account for more classification outputs. Furthermore, acquiring discriminative fingerprints of reference points at high resolution presents a substantial challenge as adjacent reference points may generate similar CSI measurements, complicating the task of achieving precise indoor localisation.

The research presented in [11] by Ruan et al. introduces a novel approach to indoor localisation for UE in 5G NR networks, utilising a DL architecture for processing CSI into more discriminative features. This work also leverages the concept of location fingerprinting. However, Ruan et al.'s contribution lie in the innovative design and implementation of their DL network, Hi-Loc, which distinguishes itself through its complex feature extraction and attention mechanisms. Hi-Loc comprises 14 layers, incorporating a comprehensive feature enrichment mechanism designed to extract features from CSI measurements. These features include the Energy of Direct Path (EDP), Effective CSI [12], and Skewness and Kurtosis [13] of CSI, each contributing valuable information regarding the signal's propagation characteristics. Such detailed feature extraction enhances the capturing of the complex interactions of radio signals with the indoor environment, which are influenced by factors like multipath propagation and obstacles. Following the feature enrichment, the Hi-Loc architecture utilises a Feature Attention module, which intelligently weighs the importance of different features, enhancing the model's focus on the most relevant information for localisation. This is complemented by a Bi-Directional Long Short-Term Memory (Bi-Directional LSTM) module, which processes the temporal sequence of CSI data, capturing the dynamic changes in signal characteristics as the UE moves within the indoor environment. The inclusion of a Sample Attention module further refines the model's input by prioritising data samples based on their significance to the localisation task, ensuring that the model's predictions are based on the most informative inputs. The final part of the DL architecture is a Fully Connected Network and Location Estimation module, which integrates the processed features to estimate the X and Y coordinates of the UE. Tested in an indoor office environment, the Hi-Loc model achieved mean positioning errors between 0.65 m and 1.03 m.

The current body of research on indoor UE positioning utilising 5G NR technologies, particularly through the application of ML and DL algorithms, is notably limited. This contrasts with the more extensive literature on indoor positioning systems that primarily focus on established wireless communication protocols such as WiFi and Bluetooth [9] [14] [15] [16]. The scarcity of studies on 5G NR-based positioning reflects the emerging nature of 5G technology in the context of indoor localisation and the unique challenges it presents, including the need for new algorithms and system designs that can effectively leverage 5G's advanced capabilities. Table 1 summarises the indoor positioning applications found in the literature comparing the data acquisition methods, parameters considered for ML and DL input, ML or DL network in use and the results.

As it can be seen, the deployment of multiple BS in a matrix array enhances the accuracy even when using a limited number of layers in the DL network. On the other hand, when using a single BS, the complexity of the DL network has to be increased to enhance the discriminative features of the received CSI samples to obtain similar positioning accuracies. The reference point (fingerprint) classification method has a high accuracy, but the complexity of the model also increases with the

resolution of reference points since the DL network will have multiple possible outputs, which can significantly decrease the model's performance.

Table 1 - ML & DL enhanced indoor UE positioning applications based on 5G radio sensing

Reference	Dataset acquisition method	Deployment	ML/DL input parameters	ML/DL network used	Results
[5]	Location fingerprinting	Matrix array deployment of BS	CIR RSRP 256 values	4-layer residual CNN, regression	-0.28m accuracy without data truncation -0.35m accuracy with data truncation
[8]	Location fingerprinting	Multiple indoor BS deployment	CSI ADCPM	4-layer DNN, classification	-96% positioning accuracy
[11]	Location fingerprinting	Single indoor BS deployment	CSI with DL enriched features EDP, Effective CSI, Kurtosis, Skewness	14-layer NN with feature enhancement, Feature attention module, Bi-Directional LSTM, Sample Attention module, fully connected layer	-0.65 to 1.03 m positioning accuracy

3.4.2 Outdoor UE positioning enhancement using ML and DL algorithms

In [17], Majid et al., explore the enhancement of UE positioning accuracy in LOS scenarios within 5G networks through DL networks. The DL algorithm proposed by the authors leverages Reference Signal Received Power (RSRP) measurements, either from the UE's serving cell alone or in association with neighbouring cells, to pinpoint the UE's location. To simulate realistic 5G base station beam communications and the associated multipath propagation effects, the authors employ a ray tracing simulator. Their test setup includes eight BSs positioned at a height of 10 m, arranged in a matrix array with 110 m between rows and 200 m between columns. This setup mimics the distribution of base stations in a typical urban 5G network environment. Each base station is equipped to emit predefined beams, covering multiple sectors and ensuring comprehensive coverage of the area. A number of 123,768 predefined locations within the test area were sampled for RSRP values at a resolution of 1 meter between points. The input data for the DL algorithm consists of four beam IDs, the corresponding four RSRP values, and the Cell ID, providing a detailed image of signal strength across the network between the UE and the adjacent BS. The study reveals that utilising only the RSRP measurements from the serving cell, paired with a DL network featuring a single hidden layer, results in a positioning error of approximately 5 m. However, incorporating RSRP measurements from neighbouring cells significantly improves accuracy, reducing positioning errors to 2 m. The most accurate results, with a positioning error of just 1.5 m, were obtained by combining data from both the serving cell and neighbouring cells while also increasing the number of hidden layers within the

DL network. Despite these promising results, the scalability of this approach faces challenges. Specifically, each new deployment area necessitates a preliminary mapping of RSRP values and subsequent retraining of the DL network to ensure accuracy. This requirement could potentially limit the practical application of such DL-assisted positioning systems in dynamic or rapidly changing environments where base station configurations or environmental conditions vary over time.

In [18] Magnus et al. analyse how ML and DL algorithms can improve the outdoor positioning accuracy of UE in 5G networks, addressing both LOS and NLOS scenarios. Utilising an Ericsson 5G testbed, the study leverages advanced technological setups to create a robust dataset for training and evaluating these algorithms. The testbed operates at a carrier frequency of 15 GHz, featuring an antenna with two 8x8 element arrays capable of generating 48 distinct beams. Each beam has a specified horizontal and vertical width, 6 degrees and 5 degrees, respectively, allowing for precise beamforming and signal directionality. To gather data, the researchers averaged ten Beam Reference Signal Received Power (BRSRP) measurements and one GNSS position measurement for each sample. This methodology ensures a real-world scenario dataset that reflects the complex dynamics of signal propagation in outdoor environments. From this primary dataset, a secondary dataset is derived by treating each vertical layer of the antenna array as an individual antenna. This approach facilitates the calculation of the Direction of Departure (DoD) based on the highest registered BRSRP, adding another layer of detail to the dataset. The input features for the ML and DL algorithms include BRSRP, DoD, and the differences in BRSRP and DoD, providing a comprehensive set of parameters for positioning analysis. The study's findings highlight the potential and limitations of using ML and DL for 5G UE positioning. Employing a Random Forest algorithm, the researchers achieved a positioning error of 9.5 m in NLOS scenarios and an accuracy of 0.898 m in LOS scenarios. However, when utilising a Neural Network, the positioning error increased to 22 m for NLOS scenarios and 3.6 m for LOS scenarios.

In [19] Klus et al. introduces an approach towards enhancing UE positioning accuracy and optimising handover processes in 5G NR networks through the application of DL techniques. This research employs the use of RSRP measurements from the Synchronization Signal, which is a critical component of the 5G NR standards defined by the 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP) [20]. These signals are periodically broadcast every 20 ms, serving as a basis for the proposed positioning algorithm. Also, by using the measurements of RSRP values from the Synchronization Signal, the functioning of the 5G network is not affected. To build a comprehensive dataset for training and evaluating their DL model, the authors have taken RSRP measurements at intervals of 0.36 s. This sampling method corresponds to a realistic mobility scenario, assuming an average UE moving speed of 5 km/h (walking speed), resulting in a distance resolution of 0.48 m, which is critical for achieving high positioning accuracy in dynamic network environments. The core of their methodology is a DL network comprising five hidden layers, designed to process 224 RSRP measurements as input vectors. The depth of this network is indicative of the complex nonlinear relationships between the input RSRP measurements and the UE's positional coordinates. From the presented results, the method employed by the authors achieved an accuracy of 1.5 m in UE positioning.

According to the research papers presented above, we can see that a variety of methodologies have been developed for outdoor UE positioning within 5G networks, yet this field remains substantially underexplored. Examination of existing literature reveals that urban NLOS scenarios continue to pose significant challenges to certain methodologies. Furthermore, numerous studies have employed ray tracing software to simulate 5G signal propagation in urban contexts for location fingerprinting. This approach facilitates a simplified method for creating datasets essential for the training and evaluation of ML and DL algorithms. Nonetheless, it is important to acknowledge that these datasets may not fully capture the complexities of real-world signal propagation environments.

Furthermore, methodologies based on 5G testbeds have demonstrated lower levels of positioning

accuracy, predominantly due to the deployment of a singular BS. Despite this limitation, the achieved positioning accuracies remain competitive when compared to those offered by conventional GNSS. From a DL network perspective, it has been observed that Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) models and Auto-Encoders deliver superior positioning accuracies. Moreover, the combining of joint measurements from multiple BSs substantially enhances the precision of positioning, as it facilitates the characterisation of the location fingerprint from diverse points. Nevertheless, as previously noted, the method of location fingerprinting commonly employed in these applications presents several challenges. There is no assurance that a location will retain an identical fingerprint over time, necessitating the retraining of the network with newly acquired location fingerprints for updates. Additionally, the methodology of generating datasets based on ray tracing has not yet been tested in practical real live scenarios, raising question marks on its applicability for real-world implementation. Methods for dataset generation that utilise measurements from real-life User Equipment subscribers, including data on Channel State Information, Channel Impulse Response, Received Signal Strength Power, Serving Cell ID, and GPS position, could be employed for the continuous update of location fingerprints. However, this approach is dependable upon the accuracy of GPS data and raises concerns regarding security and the privacy of subscribers.

Table 2 summarises the outdoor positioning applications in the literature, comparing the data acquisition methods, parameters considered for ML and DL input, and the results of the ML or DL network in use.

Table 2 - ML & DL enhanced UE positioning applications based on 5G radio sensing

Reference	Dataset acquisition method	Deployment	ML/DL input parameters	ML/DL network used	Results
[15]	Ray tracing-based location fingerprinting	Matrix array deployment of BS	Beam ID RSRP BS Cell ID	2 Hidden Layer DNN	-1.5 m positioning accuracy
[16]	5G testbed real-life location fingerprinting	Single BS	BRSRP DoD	Random Forest Neural Network	-9.5 m NLOS and 0.9 m LOS accuracy using Random Forest
[17]	Ray tracing-based location fingerprinting	Multiple outdoor BS deployment	RSRP 224 samples	5 Hidden Layer DNN	-1.5 m positioning accuracy in both LOS and NLOS scenario

3.5 Impact of hardware impairments

3.5.1 Hardware impairments and antenna calibration

Hardware impairments that impact the performance of communication, positioning, and sensing algorithms include antenna phase offset, carrier frequency offset, IQ imbalance, time accuracy offset, time jitter, beam-steering offset, power amplifier nonlinearity, and phase noise [21] [22].

The computational load and complexity of multi-cell positioning techniques involving coordination, reference signal management and measurement from multiple base stations and transmission/reception points (TRPs) are much higher than single-cell methods. For instance, the

multi-round-trip time (multi-RTT) method may appear attractive for outdoor positioning with macro base stations. However, multi-RTT requires several TRPs to measure and decode multiple uplink sounding reference signals (SRS) transmitted by a single UE device (in 3GPP, evaluations have been done with simulations with 21 cells), although only a small fraction of the TRP-UE pairs result in accurate range measurements. Moreover, with uplink methods (including multi-RTT, which uses both UL and DL signals), the time-frequency resources required for positioning grow linearly with the number of UE devices since each UE transmits a dedicated reference signal. This is not the case with methods that are based on downlink positioning reference signals (DL-PRS), which are broadcast by base stations [23] [24].

Due to computational load and complexity reasons, UL methods may be better suited for indoor deployments and more confined spaces. Specifically, for UL time-difference-of-arrival (UL-TDOA) positioning methods, irregular antenna patterns add significant impairment on positioning accuracy. Both the UEs and the network TRPs are known to have irregular antenna patterns. Due to such irregular antenna patterns, local peaks and nulls up to 5 dB can be observed in the dominant direction. As a result, irregular antenna patterns can make the UL time of arrival (UL-ToA) and UL-TdoA estimations -- which typically employ Lo's peak detection schemes -- difficult even in favourable propagation conditions. Another consequence of irregular antenna patterns is that the LoS path power can hardly be used for estimating the UE-to-TRP range since the received power is affected by the antenna irregularities [25].

Another significant source of error in positioning due to hardware impairments is the radio front-end filter delays, which can add several nanoseconds of uncertainty to ToA measurements. In contrast to the antenna pattern anomalies, the front-end filter delays can be compensated for if their values are measured in a controlled environment, such as in an anechoic chamber. Anechoic chamber-based filter calibration is, unfortunately, impractical in local deployments. As an alternative, it has been suggested to estimate the filter delays in operational networks, although such calibration schemes in live deployments need further verifications [26].

3.5.2 Synchronisation Issues

For DL or UL TdoA positioning the network nodes need to be tightly synchronised with each other. Recall that the resulting positioning error from every nanosecond synchronisation error is in the order of 30 cm, depending on the geometric dilution of precision (GDOP) associated with the measurement setup, reference signals, employed estimation scheme and other factors. For communication purposes, the 3GPP has defined that the maximum synchronisation error between non-co-located network nodes is $3\mu\text{s}$ for New Radio systems, which is on a different order and insufficient for positioning and sensing purposes with reasonable accuracy requirements [27].

For systems using the Precision Time Protocol (PTP) for synchronisation, the synchronisation accuracy at the antenna can vary a lot depending on how much accuracy budget must be reserved for the PTP time distribution. Therefore, in outdoor deployments, where the PTP is used to synchronise the nodes of a radio access network, the base stations can synchronise to external clock sources, such as Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) signals.

Accurate synchronisation plays a key role in carrier-phase positioning (CPP), since CPP methods using the RF carrier phase have similarities with coherent joint transmission (C-JT) for communications. Specifically, both CPP and C-JT rely on high-quality phase stability over a longer period. In 5G, one approach for C-JT is based on regular feedback from the UE devices (e.g., with a periodicity of 30ms) measuring the relative RF phase at its receiver. Reporting the relative RF phase periodically to the BS enables it to adjust the transmitted DL signals towards the UE devices to coherently add up at the intended UE receiver. The relative RF phase between the involved BSs in the C-JT must be stable

between regular periodic correction events. ts. The majority of currently deployed systems are not designed for strict inter-node phase stability for C-JT. C-JT-related phase corrections targeting a specific UE may cause issues for CPP-based positioning by the same UE since the correction may affect the CPP algorithm [28].

4 Project requirements matrix definition and target KPIs/KVIs

This section outlines the project activities centred around determining the target KPIs and KVIs that will be measured and challenged during the implementation phase in the context of WP6.

4.1 State-of-the-art review

The state-of-the-art in network and service KPIs for 6G integrated sensing and communications technologies is shaped by contributions from several key research initiatives and standardisation activities, notably within 3GPP, 5G PPP, and Horizon Europe projects like HEXA-X.

In 3GPP standardisation activities [29], enhancements in Release 17 focus on refining the metrics crucial for enhancing user experience and technology capabilities in future 6G environments, including the support for integrated localisation and sensing services. Key localisation KPIs include improved horizontal and vertical accuracy, aimed at delivering precise location information essential in dense urban contexts and for various applications like navigation and automated systems. The target for horizontal accuracy seeks to achieve refined accuracy within a few meters, adaptable to both outdoor and indoor settings. Another critical KPI, latency, encompasses both Physical Layer Latency and Higher Layer Latency, which are vital for applications that demand real-time updates on positioning to ensure quick responsiveness. Additionally, network and device efficiency metrics assess the resource utilisation during localisation tasks, aiming to minimise energy consumption and optimise data transmission. These enhancements reflect 3GPP's commitment to support a broad spectrum of applications by advancing the reliability, accuracy, and efficiency of NR positioning, which are instrumental in shaping the robust capabilities anticipated for 6G technologies.

The 5G PPP's work [30], particularly through the ICT-52 projects, focuses on defining and measuring new KPIs that will be essential for 6G. The projects under ICT-52, such as HEXA-X, aim at advancing technologies that support dynamic resourcing, connectivity, and network intelligence using AI models. These efforts emphasise the importance of developing KPIs that cater to enhanced network capabilities, sustainability, and intelligent resource management. Notable focus areas include energy efficiency, service reliability, and computational optimization, all crucial for the anticipated 6G services.

As detailed in [31], the HEXA-X project particularly focuses on innovative localization and sensing services, setting target values for localization accuracy that are foundational for 6G's operational capabilities.

Localisation accuracy, a critical metric for the effectiveness of various 6G applications, has been targeted to achieve a range of 10-20 cm. This accuracy is vital for applications involving precise positioning and tracking, which are anticipated to be commonplace in 6G environments. The importance of this KPI is underscored by its role in supporting advanced use cases, from industrial automation to urban mobility solutions, where precise localisation can significantly enhance operational efficiency and safety.

The HEXA-X project documents also discuss the integration of localization with communication technologies, which helps in overcoming challenges like signal blockage and optimising spectral efficiency. This integration is crucial for ensuring that localisation services in 6G are not only accurate but also resilient and efficient, capable of supporting the high reliability and low latency requirements typical of next-generation wireless systems.

Moreover, these documents highlight the development of new sensing capabilities, which complement localization by providing rich contextual information necessary for applications such as

autonomous driving, remote surgery, and more dynamic and interactive augmented reality environments. The combination of highly accurate localisation and comprehensive sensing, facilitated by 6G technologies, is set to redefine the interaction paradigms across a multitude of sectors.

Thus, the focus on achieving high localisation accuracy and the enhancement of sensing capabilities form a cornerstone of the KPIs for future 6G technologies, reflecting a broader shift towards more integrated, reliable, and context-aware communication systems.

In this context, the following section will describe the 6G-MUSICAL target KPI values based on the specific characteristics of the technologies and algorithms that will be implemented in the project's scope.

4.2 Definition of KPIs and KVs for the project

4.2.1 KPIs

Defining minimum technical performance requirements, which present the 6G radio interface KPIs, is ongoing at the United Nations-based International Telecommunication Union Radiocommunication sector in 2024-2025. The starting point for the KPI definition work is the capabilities of 6G (IMT-2030) listed in Recommendation ITU-R M.2160 from ITU-R:

- Enhanced capabilities from 5G: Peak data rate, User-experienced data rate, Spectrum efficiency, Area traffic capacity, Connection Density, Mobility, Latency, Reliability, Security and resilience
- New capabilities not used for 5G: Coverage, Positioning, Sensing-related capabilities, Applicable AI-related capabilities, Sustainability, Interoperability

These KPIs will be assigned numerical target values or qualitative characterisations in 2024-2025. The KPIs on positioning, sensing-related capabilities, and sustainability will be particularly relevant for 6G-MUSICAL.

4.2.2 KVs

In addition to KPIs, values-driven technology development has become increasingly important for 6G, resulting in the notion of key values and KVs. 6G technologies are poised to revolutionise communication and sensing capabilities, where KVs play a central role in defining their societal and economic impacts, as shown in the common EU-US vision for 6G [32] and in the HEXA-X Horizon Europe project deliverables on future 6G-based localisation services [31]. Integrated sensing and communication in 6G are expected to provide high-precision localisation and environmental awareness, crucial for applications such as autonomous driving, industrial automation, and personalised healthcare. These advancements hinge on achieving stringent KVs like trustworthiness, sustainability, inclusiveness, and interoperability.

Trustworthiness in 6G encompasses security, privacy, dependability, and safety, ensuring that the technologies are reliable and safeguard user data against unauthorised access and cyber threats. The integrated nature of 6G networks requires robust encryption and secure communication protocols to protect the integrity and confidentiality of data transmitted across increasingly complex networks.

Sustainability refers to the environmental, social and economic impact of 6G technologies. Regarding environmental sustainability, 6G aims to minimise energy consumption and carbon footprint, promoting technologies that are not only more energy-efficient but also capable of facilitating reduced energy usage across various sectors through more intelligent network operations and architectures.

Inclusiveness in 6G technology development ensures that the benefits of these advanced technologies are accessible to all segments of the population, including underserved and rural communities. This involves developing cost-effective solutions and promoting widespread adoption to prevent a digital divide.

Finally, interoperability and openness are key to ensuring that 6G systems can seamlessly integrate with existing and future technologies, facilitating a global standard that supports a wide range of applications and services. This requires collaborative efforts in standardisation bodies and between stakeholders to develop open, transparent, and scalable technologies.

Realising these KVIs will require concerted efforts in multidisciplinary R&D, standardisation, and policymaking to ensure that 6G technologies can meet the diverse needs of future digital societies while aligning with global standards and ethical guidelines.

The evolution of 6G integrated sensing and communications technologies is expected to significantly advance capabilities across various use cases, with KVIs playing a pivotal role in their development and implementation. For target use cases such as 3D mapping of connected and unconnected objects, drone detection, weather sensing, and the operation of autonomous guided vehicles (AGVs) and autonomous cars, the KVIs focus on enhancing the reliability, privacy, energy efficiency, and sustainability of commercial ISAC systems.

Reliability is a critical KVI, especially for weather sensing and the operation of AGVs and autonomous vehicles, which require uninterrupted and accurate data to make real-time decisions critical for safety and operational efficiency. Ensuring consistent performance under varying conditions and scenarios, including adverse weather or in densely built areas, underpins this KVI.

Security and privacy are also vital KVIs, especially as these technologies often handle sensitive location and identification data that could pose privacy risks or become targets for cyber-attacks. Ensuring data integrity and securing communication channels against unauthorised access is necessary to protect individual privacy and system integrity.

Energy efficiency and sustainability are increasingly important KVIs, particularly as global energy consumption concerns rise. Developing 6G technologies that maximise performance while minimising energy use and environmental impact is essential, particularly in systems deployed at scale, such as in city-wide AGV networks or connected vehicle infrastructure.

These KVIs define the performance and ethical benchmarks for deploying 6G ISAC technologies and guide the research and regulatory framework that will support their sustainable and equitable integration into everyday use. Ensuring these KVIs are met will be crucial for successfully adopting 6G technologies in complex and critical applications.

In this approach, the 6G-MUSICAL project defined a set of target KVIs mapped to each of the selected ISAC use cases, as showcased in Table 3.

Table 3 - Initial set of target KVIs

Societal	
KVI 1: Safety	x
KVI 2: Security	x
KVI 4: Privacy	x
KVI 5: Trustworthiness	x
Environmental	
KVI 6: Reduction of CO2 emissions	x
Economical	

KVI 8: Affordability	x
KVI 9: Business value	x

4.3 Mapping of the requirements and performance figures into radio parameters

A set of KPIs has been proposed in the project. These KPIs have to be mapped to technology-based requirements. The proposed accuracy requires specific technological KPIs, which depend on the proposed implementation and proof-of-concept demonstrators. The PoC demonstrators are based on two technologies, which dictate different KPIs. IMEC will demonstrate an ISAC system based on Open WiFi, and UCL and IT, with support from Menhir, will demonstrate an optical/wireless technological demonstrator.

The target setup for the Open WiFi demonstrator will use three nodes based on the WiFi 6 standard; the bandwidth will be 20MHz, and the carrier frequency will be between 70MHz and 6GHz. In terms of the KPIs, the target values are listed in Table 4. As can be seen, the localisation and tracking accuracy will be $\leq 1\text{m}$, this KPI being achievable in the PoC phase with good SNR settings. Regarding resolution, the target system bandwidth provides a sensing resolution of 7.5m, which should be improved using multi-static sensing. Due to only three nodes, the improvement will be lower than expected (i.e., 7.5/2 m); therefore, we expect a sensing resolution better than 7.5m in the OpenWiFi demonstrator.

Table 4 - OpenWiFi demonstrator KPIs

KPIs	Possible in POC	In the proposal
Localisation accuracy	$\leq 1\text{m}$	$\leq 1\text{m}$
Tracking accuracy	$\leq 1\text{m}$	$\leq 1\text{m}$
Resolution	$< 7.5\text{ m}$	2x better than the state of the art for 3D imaging (no value given).

For the Optical and wireless PoC, the proposed KPI matrix is based on the design and parameters below. The general complex is simply generating a comb of optical frequencies using an accurately generated optical clock (using Menhir's system), then using the clock to drive/reference a set of modulators implemented using an field-programmable gate array (FPGA) and then converting the electrical signals back to optical, multiplexing these and transmitting this over a fibre. the key advantage of this technique is generating signals with exceptionally small phase noise that will result in low jitter and highly synchronous signals at the receiver, and which will facilitate cm level localisation accuracy.

Table 5, Table 6, Table 7 and Table 8 outline the technological specifications derived from the proposal KPIs, which we aim to produce in the proof-of-concept demonstrator.

Table 5 - Optical/Wireless Demonstrator Proposal KPIs

Proposed KPIs	Comment	
Frequency range	sub-6GHz-100GHz	KPI 3.1 (pag.10, 28)
Phase noise	$< -110\text{ dBc/Hz}$	KPI 3.1 (pag.10, 28)
Timing Clock Jitter	$< 100\text{fs}$	KPI 3.2 (pag.10, 28) From sub 6GHz to 100GHz
Relative Timing Jitter	$< 500\text{fs}$	KPI 3.2 (pag.10, 28) From sub 6GHz to 100GHz

Clock timing error	< 50ps	compared to existing synchronization schemes for edge nodes, KPI 3.3 (pag.11, 29)
Time accuracy	$1e^{-13}$ of relative accuracy at 1s	at least two orders of magnitude better than existing reference sources used for clock and RF/mm frequencies. KPI 3.4 (pag.11, 29)
Inter-node timing deviation	< 30ps	KPI 3.5 (pag.11, 29)

Table 6 - Master optical clock measurement KPIs

Central wavelength	1550.1 nm	As discussed at the meeting
Spectral bandwidth at -3 dB	> 10 nm	Taking from specs at MENHIR-1550 SERIES datasheet
Repetition Rate / Fundamental Frequency	2.5 GHz	As discussed at the meeting
Phase noise at 100 kHz to 10 MHz	< -110 dBc/Hz at all carrier frequencies	It was defined as Phase Noise < -110 dBc/Hz at KPI 3.1
Average Optical Output Power	> 50 mW (Up to 2W)	MENHIR-1550 MENHIR-1550+ (Oscillator with amplifier) Which one will be supplied?
Optical Output Power per discrete line	-30dBm	It will be dependent of the option

Table 7 - Multichannel transmitter and receiver produced InP PIC KPIs

Central wavelength	1550 nm	Comments
Optical bandwidth Channel Passband	0.2 nm ± 0.10 nm	It will depend on the foundry process used, namely the AWGs for MUX and DEMUX.
Channel Isolation	> 30 dB	It will depend on foundry process used namely the AWGs for MUX and DEMUX.
Electrical Bandwidth	> 6 GHz	The electrical bandwidth will be \sim the bw of the OFDM baseband signal or $> 2x$ if it is sent in the IF band. 5GHz should be enough
Output Optical Power (Tx)	> 0 dBm	We are considering short-reach application (up to 2km) with some margin for power splitting, however, it depends on the receiver sensitivity
Sensitivity (Rx)	< -15dBm	N/A
Spurious-free dynamic range (SFDR)	> 60 dB	N/A

Table 8 - Remote ISAC transceivers (RISACTs) KPIs

Output RF Power	> 2W (> 30dBm)	It will depend on the testbed, radar cross section, receiver sensitivity, antennas gain
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RF Receiver sensitivity	< -50 dBm	It will depend on the testbed, radar cross section, receiver sensitivity, antennas gain. Minimum Detectable Signal in radars can go up to -100dBm
Instantaneous Dynamic range	> 50 dB	Note. In practice systems dynamic range greater that 80 dB may be required, it depends on the clutter signal intensity
SFDR	> 60 dB	Suppose some degradation

5 6G-MUSICAL Proof-Of-Concepts Developments

This chapter aims to offer an updated and detailed view of the PoCs that will be developed in the scope of the 6G-MUSICAL project to demonstrate the technological advancements researched within WP3-to-5.

5.1 Cooperative Communication and Multi-Static Sensing Based on OFDM Waveforms

5.1.1 Objectives and Motivation

This PoC will validate algorithms developed for cooperative multi-static sensing by demonstrating:

1. Synchronized data collection in a distributed setup with FPGA based customised WiFi nodes (AP + multiple Stations) for joint multi-static sensing and communication.
2. Centralized data processing algorithm for advanced sensing features, such as high-accuracy localisation/tracking and 3D (three-dimensional) imaging.

The IEEE802.11 WiFi technology, widely used for indoor wireless networks, has not only evolved together with 5G/6G but also shares lots of similar features, such as OFDM and OFDMA, which make it attractive for testing multi-static sensing algorithms. Several factors need consideration when using multiple WiFi nodes for multi-static sensing, such as the signal needs to be collected coherently at different nodes, and the centralised algorithm should be able to handle RF impairment and synchronisation error/stability among the multiple nodes. In this PoC, the FPGA-based WiFi platform (openwifi: the open-source WiFi chip project) will be extended with the distributed synchronisation and data collection capability. The in-node (PHY and MAC) and centralised algorithm developed in WP4 will be integrated with the openwifi and use a standardised waveform (OFDM of IEEE802.11a/g/n/ax) to demonstrate the capability of communicating and sensing in a distributed setup.

5.1.2 Infrastructure Baseline to be Used and Components to be Tested

IMEC developed and open-sourced the openwifi project at the end of 2019, which is the full-stack FPGA implementation of IEEE802.11 on the SDR platform (easy to be improved/customised) and uses the FPGA WiFi NIC (Network Interface Card) in the same way as other COTS (Commercial Off the Shelf) WiFi cards. It supports WiFi4 (802.11n) and WiFi6 (802.11ax). Besides the standard WiFi functionalities, it also supports many unique/advanced features, such as hardware timestamping, deep physical layer info (CSI, Frequency Offset, RF status) exposing, separated full duplex Tx/Rx antennas, etc., which are very useful for Joint Sensing and Communication research but do not exist on normal COTS WiFi cards. For this PoC, we will use the clock source with multiple outputs to synchronise multiple openwifi nodes. The Ettus OCTOCLOCK equipment could be the candidate. In each openwifi board, the configurable RF Lo PLL, ADC PLL and FPGA baseband processing algorithms can be configured to emulate the different synchronisation errors in the different distributed deployment scenarios. The existing openwifi side channel link between the FPGA and Host computer can be used as the baseline functionality for data collection.

In this PoC, the following items will be tested:

1. The baseband algorithms developed/optimised for both sensing and communication in WP4 will be deployed and tested in the openwifi platform.
2. The centralised multi-static sensing algorithm, developed in WP4, will be tested.

5.1.3 Validation scenario description and KPIs to be validated

This PoC aims to show ISAC in a cell-free wireless network context with a WiFi OFDM waveform. Figure 3 illustrates the typical setup of this PoC.

Figure 3 - PoC typical setup for ISAC in a cell-free wireless network context with WiFi OFDM waveform

Three openwifi stations will be used in this PoC; each station could work in either AP or client mode. The following multi-static configurations will be considered in the PoC:

1. Transmit a communication signal with STA1 and measure the reflected signal by STA1's RX antenna (monostatic mode) or another STA3 that is close to STA1 (bistatic mode) to generate range profiles and/or range-Doppler maps. The measurement will use the preamble and/or the payload for sensing purposes.
2. Transmit with STA1 and receive and decode the data by STA2 in the presence of a fixed or moving target in the channel between STA1 and STA2. STA2 generates range profiles and/or range-Doppler maps showing the target.
3. The same experiment in 2) is repeated, combining measurements from multiple STAs to generate multi-static range profiles and/or range-Doppler maps. This should increase the resolution beyond the bi-static range resolution because of the different viewing angles of the receiving STAs.

5.1.4 Implementation planning and development activities

The overall planning related to this PoC is that:

- The low-level algorithm (MAC & PHY on an openwifi board) and the centralised sensing algorithm will be developed in parallel in WP4 during M5 ~ M29. The PoC work will be carried out during M15 ~ M35, among which M15 ~ M24 are for planning, M21 ~ M30 are for implementation, and M31 ~ M35 are for performance evaluation.

Regarding the PoC-related algorithm development activities:

- The low-level algorithms will mainly cover the radar-aware WiFi receiver mode switching algorithm, Time-frequency sync algorithm, self-calibration algorithm, and data cleaning algorithm. The main purpose of the low-level algorithm is to ensure the collected sensing data (IQ sample, CSI, etc.) is useable for the central sensing algorithm.

Regarding the PoC development activities:

- During the planning phase (M15 ~ M24), initial exploration will be done to decide the main PoC conditions: hardware platform, antenna type, frequency and bandwidth, and data format between low-level and central algorithms.
- During the implementation phase (M21 ~ M30), the PoC components, i.e., the algorithms and the hardware, will be integrated. Multiple experiments will be conducted to iterate and improve the functionalities, data collection and algorithms.
- During the evaluation phase (M31 ~ M35), the algorithm and the PoC setup will be fine-tuned according to the evaluation criteria.

5.2 Generation and Robust Distribution of References to Synchronise Network

5.2.1 Objectives and Motivation

This PoC will validate algorithms developed for cooperative multi-static sensing using widely distributed antennas by synchronising the Edge nodes with ISAC signals. It will demonstrate the importance of using microwave photonics and photonic integrated circuit (PIC) technology to:

1. Generate a very precise clock reference with ultra-low phase noise.
2. Point-to-multipoint synchronisation for massive MIMO edge network with ultra-low timing jitter at a range of frequencies extending up to the mm-wave.
3. Demonstration of SWaP-C reducing by using PIC and sharing the photonic core among several sensors.

Radar systems, GPS, and various other sensing and localisation technologies rely on generating and correlating RF signals. Achieving more precise localisation (sub-cm), including 3D imaging, imposes stringent requirements on the reference clock's phase noise and timing jitter. The reference clock must be synchronised with ISAC signals at edge nodes. Previous research has shown that microwave photonic solutions are superior for low-phase noise and ultra-low timing jitter, outperforming quartz-based RF generators. Additionally, transmitting RF signals via optical fibre offers significantly higher performance than traditional coaxial RF cables. However, these photonic technologies must still be demonstrated and assessed in ISAC systems with sub-cm sensing. This proof of concept will showcase photonic solutions for generating and distributing reference signals, including ISAC signals, to edge nodes, addressing the future demands of ultra-precise sensing.

5.2.2 Infrastructure baseline to be used and components to be tested

The PoC will be integrated into the Optical Radio Convergence Research Infrastructure for

Communications and Power Delivering (ORCIP)¹, belonging to the roadmap of research infrastructures. This research infrastructure combines physical testing and simulations and will be accessible remotely. It is equipped with the most advanced equipment in radio and optical communications, such as vector signal analysers (VSAs) and vector network analysers (VNAs) up to 110GHz, real-time oscilloscopes (RTOs) with sampling frequencies up to 200 GSa/s, arbitrary waveform generators up to 120 GSa/s and FPGAs with Radio Frequency System-on-Chip (RFSoc).

In this PoC, the following subunits will be tested:

1. **Master Optical Clock**, based on a photonic frequency comb generator, will be tested to ensure that it can generate a series of discrete equally spaced lines in the frequency domain with high coherency and ultra-low phase noise in the subfemtosecond RMS timing jitter. The KPIs that will be measured are:
 - Central wavelength
 - Spectral bandwidth at -3 dB
 - Repetition rate
 - Phase noise
 - Optical Output Power per discrete line
 - Average Optical Output Power
2. **The Multichannel Transmitter and Receiver** produced InP PIC will be characterised in chip and after packaged in terms of:
 - Central wavelengths
 - Optical bandwidth
 - Channel Isolation
 - Electrical Bandwidth
 - Output Optical Power (Tx)
 - Sensitivity (Rx)
 - Spurious-free dynamic range (SFDR)
3. **The Remote ISAC transceivers (RISACTs)** will be electrically characterised in terms of:
 - Output RF power
 - SFDR
 - RF Receiver sensitivity
 - Instantaneous dynamic range
4. **Optical links** will be characterised in terms of:
 - Insertion loss
 - Propagation delay
 - Thermal coefficient of delay
5. **Complete transmission and acquisition system**, including FPGA RFSoc, will be characterised in terms of:
 - Clock phase noise and timing jitter at the Edge nodes

¹ <http://www.orcip.pt/>

- Relative jitter for carrier frequency synchronisation
- Time accuracy and Inter-node timing deviation
- Frequency Spurious characterisation
- AM to AM conversion
- AM to PM conversion
- The adequate number of bits (ENOB) at ADC and DAC converters

5.2.3 Validation scenario description and KPIs to be validated

The work will include experimental testing of all the subsystems of the data and clock distribution to the Remote ISAC transceivers depicted in Figure 4, including the Master Optical Clock based on a photonic comb generator, the multichannel TRx and Rx transceivers designed and structured as Photonic Integrated Circuits (PICs) and the Remote ISAC transceivers (RISACTs). The synchronisation and data transmission of point-to-multipoint ISAC signals will be experimentally tested. The Lab will experimentally emulate a massive MIMO edge network with more than 1000 edges.

Figure 4 - PoC 2 Synchronisation Architecture

For the generation and robust Distribution of references to Synchronize Network, we are proposing the following KPIs:

Phase noise performance (KPI 3.1): Achieve flexible coverage of frequencies to range from sub-6GHz to 100GHz for transmission and simultaneous synchronisation of both clock and RF at receivers, with levels of phase noise performance better than -110 dBc/Hz across the range.

Jitter (KPI 3.2): Achieve timing/clock jitter of <100 fs and ultra-low relative jitter <500 fs for carrier frequency synchronisation between massive MIMO edge nodes with less than 2km.

Clock timing error (KPI 3.3): Benchmark: Achieve clock synchronisation performance < 50 ps compared to existing synchronisation schemes for edge nodes.

Time accuracy (KPI 3.4): Benchmark: Achieve a level of accuracy for the developed reference source that meets 10^{-15} of relative accuracy at 1s, at least two orders of magnitude better than existing reference sources used for clock and RF/mm frequencies.

Inter-node timing deviation (KPI 3.5): Achieve inter-node timing deviation of < 30 ps to enable sub-

cm resolution compared to the clock synchronisation techniques used in massive MIMO edge networks for wireless sensing and communication.

5.2.4 Implementation planning and development activities

The overall planning related to this PoC is that:

In this PoC, the different subsystems and algorithms will be developed in parallel at different WPs. Regarding the development phase, the activities will be developed as follows:

1. PoC definition: The architecture design, technical requirements, KPIs and methodologies will be defined in WP2 (M1-M15), and delivered by M15.
2. Master Optical Clock: The design and testing of the Master Optical Clock will be carried out in WP5 (M7-M25). An initial version of the component will be delivered by M21 and reported by M25.
3. Multichannel Transmitter and Receiver: The design, implementation, and testing of the PIC will also be carried out in WP5 (M12-M27). An initial version of the component will be delivered by M21 and reported by M27.
4. Remote ISAC transceivers: The design and analysis of these transceivers will be carried out in WP5 (M5- M25), with an initial version of the component to be delivered by M21 and reported by M24.
5. Algorithms: The development of cooperative multi-static sensing algorithms will be carried out in WP4 (M5–M29), with intermediate and results on M21 and M29, respectively. Synchronisation algorithms will be developed in parallel (WP4, M5-M29), with intermediate and results by M19 and M27, respectively.

The algorithms and modules from WP3,4&5 that will be integrated in this PoC will be identified by M25.

Regarding the PoC activities, three phases are identified:

Planning phase (M15-M24): In this phase, initial exploratory work will be done to define the PoC. The necessary interfaces for integration into the ORCIP infrastructure will be defined, and M24 will establish component acceptance tests.

Implementation phase (M21-M30): In this phase, the integration of the subsystems is performed, with the initial version of the components being delivered by M21. The radio and optical units will be integrated, and the ORCIP infrastructure will be upgraded to validate the synchronisation and multi-static sensing algorithms. This phase encompasses multiple rounds of experiments to iteratively improve the algorithms, power consumption and performance.

Evaluation phase (M31-M35): In this phase, fine adjustments to the integrated subsystems will be conducted to meet the PoC objectives and KPIs.

5.3 Integrated Communication and Sensing with Planar Phased Array Antennas

5.3.1 Objectives and Motivation

The objectives of this PoC are to validate and integrate planar phased array antennas in a real 5G communication system environment and ensure their capability of transmitting and receiving signals on the 5G network. Numerous KPIs, as developed below, are used to measure the accomplishment of

those objectives.

Phased antenna array becomes an essential solution in wireless networks (RAN included). Phased array or steerable antennas can be enabled using semiconductor components, MEMS, or phase-controlled materials. We will investigate the best produce planar phased array antennas that can be easily integrated with remain circuits with reduced size, weight and power consumption (SWAp). The use of meta materials in phased array antennas is still under investigation, particularly in the industry. This technology appeals to us one of possible candidates due to its low energy consumption.

5.3.2 *5Infrastructure Baseline to be used and Components to be Tested*

Different **IT, UCL and FhG** infrastructures will be used in this PoC to characterise the RF antenna. We will use the **eBOS** and **ORO** 5G testbeds infrastructure to integrate the phased array antenna based in a real communication system environment.

In this PoC, the following items will be tested:

1. The Phased array antenna based on selected technology for 5G/B5G system will be tested.
2. The technology for phased array antenna for 5G/6G communication systems will be evaluated (efficiency, energy consumption, industrialisation process, etc.).

5.3.3 *Validation Scenario Description and KPIs to be Validated*

For the PoC, the central focus is on the following objectives:

- **Design, Validate and Integrate the phased array antenna (PAA) in a communication system infrastructure:** The antenna will function as a part of the **RAN** architecture of 5G testbed (eBOS and ORO 5G infrastructures will be used).

In the validation phase, all RF performances of the PAA will be measured and evaluated. Bandwidth, radiation behaviour and gain are the most important characteristics.

The PAA will be integrated and used as a BS (base station) antenna. The antenna will function as a part of the RAN architecture of the 5G Testbed, which is based on OAI or O-RAN. The phased array antenna will be used to transmit and receive information from mobile users, and it will support all service traffic types.

The phased array antenna **will be tested to ensure they can transmit and receive signals on the 5G network**. The infrastructure of the **eBOS** and **ORO** 5G testbeds include both optical and wireless fronthaul, which will allow the 5G RAN functionalities to be split between the BBU and RRH. **The phased array antenna will be integrated into these infrastructures and will work in conjunction with the 5G RAN functionalities to transmit and receive information from mobile users.**

- **Qualify the antenna in real-world conditions:** in this step, the qualification of the antenna will be guaranteed by controlling the following KPI's: Bandwidth, Gain, Radiation Pattern, Directivity, Polarization, VSWR and Efficiency
 - Bandwidth: Determine the frequencies that the antenna can use to transmit and receive within the 5G network's frequency range. (The antenna will be developed for mm-wave FR2 n258 band within the frequency band 24.250 - 27.5 GHz).
 - Gain: Describes how effectively the antenna radiates energy in a specific direction compared to an isotropic antenna.

- Radiation Pattern: Depicts the spatial distribution of radiated power, showing how the antenna directs energy in various directions.
- Directivity: Indicates how concentrated the radiated power is in a specific direction compared to an isotropic source.
- Polarization: Refers to the orientation of the electric field of the radiated wave.
- VSWR (Voltage Standing Wave Ratio): Represents the efficiency of impedance matching between the antenna and the transmission line/source.
- Efficiency: Describes the ratio of the radiated power to the total input power.

The PAA will be tested in a controlled environment to qualify the antenna to evaluate its performance under various operating conditions. The tests will assess the antenna's ability to maintain its beamwidth, gain, pattern radiation characteristics, and other factors that may affect its performance.

The test results will be analysed to determine if the PoC has met its objectives. If the objectives are not achieved, the partners will examine the data and decide whether any antenna or 5G Testbed infrastructure modifications are required. The design process will be iterated if modifications are required until the PoC objectives are successfully met.

5.3.4 Implementation planning and development activities

This PoC aims to integrate technology-based phased array antennas, including metamaterials, into a real 5G communication system environment, assessing their transmission and reception capabilities within the 5G network. The main goal is to achieve high performance with respect to bandwidth, radiation behaviour, gain, and other critical KPIs while ensuring the antenna's compatibility with ISAC systems. In this approach, several PoC phases were identified:

Planning Phase (M15 - M20)

Initial exploratory work will identify the critical components and configurations for the PoC, including:

- Selection of the hardware platform and antenna type, including the use of metamaterials.
- Determination of the frequency range and bandwidth requirements for mmWave band.

Implementation Phase (M21 - M30)

This phase focuses on the integration and iterative testing of the PoC components:

- Integration of developed phased array antenna developed by FHG into the eBOS or ORO 5G testbeds and configuration to function as part of the RAN architecture.
- Multiple rounds of testing under controlled conditions to assess the antenna's performance, including its ability to maintain beamwidth, gain, and radiation patterns.
- Iterative improvements based on testing results to enhance the efficiency, energy consumption, and overall performance of the antenna system.

Evaluation Phase (M31 - M35)

Final adjustments and performance evaluations will be conducted to ensure all PoC objectives are met:

- Comprehensive assessment of RF performance, including bandwidth, coverage, and spectral

efficiency.

- Qualifying the antenna under real-world conditions to confirm its operational stability and effectiveness over large areas.
- Final analysis of test results to confirm whether the PoC objectives have been achieved or if further modifications are necessary.

Upon successfully completing and verifying the PoC objectives, the phased array antenna will be considered for future implementation in 6G networks. IT, UCL, FHN, eBOS and ORO will conclude all tests and validate the outcomes, ensuring the PoC meets the set objectives and contributes effectively to advancing 5G and future network technologies. [60]

6 Use cases of interest based on the PoCs and requirements

This chapter provides an in-depth look at the potential use cases that could be implemented using the technologies developed within 6G-MUSICAL's three PoCs, providing real business opportunities for Mobile Networks Operators (MNOs). This deliverable investigates the requirements in terms of KPIs and KVs for each of the selected ISAC applications.

6.1 Positioning, localisation of connected objects

6.1.1 Use case: Indoor localisation of AGVs in warehouses and production facilities

6.1.1.1 Objectives

The primary objective is to harness 6G's ultra-reliable and low-latency communications to significantly enhance the real-time accuracy of Automated Guided Vehicles (AGVs) navigation in warehouses and production facilities. This improved localisation aims to streamline operational efficiency by integrating warehouse management systems for optimal routing and scheduling and enhancing workplace safety through advanced collision avoidance systems. The system is designed to be scalable and flexible, accommodating changes in warehouse-size or layout while maintaining high operational standards.

6.1.1.2 Description

The target system uses a network of 6G-enabled radio units placed throughout a facility to create a mesh of real-time communication points. AGVs will be equipped with 6G routers that will be able to communicate their position to the centralised control system and to receive navigational commands. The central system, powered by edge computing, will process this data to make immediate routing decisions based on current conditions, such as obstructions, human activity, and other AGVs' locations. Integration with the warehouse management system will allow for the coordination of AGVs with loading, unloading, and storage operations, optimising the overall workflow.

6.1.1.3 Requirement's Analysis (KPIs/KVIs)

KPIs

Radar-based KPIs, showcased in Table 9, are essential for the indoor localisation of AGVs in warehouses and production facilities to enable precise and reliable real-time tracking. These KPIs guarantee accurate distance and speed measurements, which are critical in complex indoor environments where AGVs must operate within limited spaces and avoid obstacles. Additionally, precise angular estimation enables AGVs to maintain the correct direction, enhancing navigation accuracy in congested environments. Low error rates, in terms of missed detections and false alarms, are vital for maintaining trust in the localisation system's reliability, reducing the risk of collisions, and ensuring a seamless flow of operations. Finally, minimised latency and regular data updates are crucial for real-time responsiveness, supporting timely adjustments to AGV paths based on environmental changes or task requirements. These KPIs collectively ensure a robust localisation framework that enhances the performance and safety of AGVs in dynamic indoor environments.

Table 9 - KPIs for indoor localisation of AGVs in warehouses and production facilities

KPI	Requirement or Values
Unambiguous Range	150 m

Unambiguous Velocity	5 m/s
Range Resolution	0.1 m
Velocity Resolution	0.05 m/s
Angle Resolution	Azimuth: 1 deg, Elevation: N/A
Angle Accuracy	Azimuth: 1 deg, Elevation: N/A
Range Accuracy	0.5 m
Velocity Accuracy	0.1 m/s
Miss-Detection	2 %
False Alarm	5 %
PHY Signal Processing Latency	2 s
Application Layer Latency	N/A
Update Rate	0.25 times per second
Availability	95 % – 99 %

KVIs

The KVIs for this use case, showcased in Table 10, address societal, environmental, and economic aspects. Safety is enhanced by enabling real-time operation and collision avoidance of AGVs. Trustworthiness is essential to ensure that the network provides reliable management of the operation of the AGVs. Environmentally, the system contributes to reducing CO₂ emissions by minimising the need for additional infrastructure, as the cellular network will support the operation. Economically, affordability is key for widespread adoption, while business value is realised through optimised workflow efficiency, reduced infrastructure and operational costs, and enhanced productivity in warehouses.

Table 10 - KVIs for indoor localisation of AGVs in warehouses and production facilities

Societal	
KVI 1: Safety	x
KVI 2: Security	N/A
KVI 4: Privacy	N/A
KVI 5: Trustworthiness	x
Environmental	
KVI 6: Reduction of CO2 emissions	x
Economical	
KVI 8: Affordability	x
KVI 9: Business value	x

6.1.2 Use case: Smart convoys

6.1.2.1 Objectives

For smart convoys, the objective is to improve road safety by utilising 6G's rapid communication capabilities to synchronise vehicles within the convoy, reducing human error and reaction times. This technology also aims to enhance traffic efficiency by maintaining optimal speeds and minimising the space between cars, thus alleviating traffic congestion and reducing emissions. The dynamic management of convoys allows vehicles to join or leave without causing disruptions, and integration with smart city infrastructure facilitates smoother interactions with traffic systems, further enhancing the effectiveness of the convoy within urban settings.

6.1.2.2 Description

Smart convoys will utilise 6G communications to enable vehicles to share status information and coordinate movements. Each vehicle in the convoy will be equipped with 6G routers that transmit its position, speed, and operational data to other convoy members and a lead vehicle. This lead vehicle will process the collective data to adjust the convoy's speed and spacing in real time. Integration with traffic management systems will allow the convoy to receive updates on road conditions and traffic, adapting its behaviour to optimise flow and safety.

6.1.2.3 Requirement's analysis (KPIs/KVIs)

KPIs

To support the smart convoy, use case, the specified KPIs in Table 11 ensure vehicles can preserve a coordinated convoy, responding rapidly to traffic conditions. The maximum unambiguous range should be sufficient to support operation across metropolitan areas, where APs are densely deployed, and rural areas, where they are sparsely distributed. The range and velocity resolutions enable the network to estimate the position of nearby vehicles and distinguish between similar velocities, which is common in smart convoys. The proposed angle resolution and accuracy allow for precise tracking and alignment. Additionally, the low rates of missed detections and false alarms reduce the possibility of misinterpreting the position of nearby vehicles and other objects, increasing reliability. With minimal latency and a regular update rate, the system allows real-time adjustments within the convoy, ensuring quick reaction times and improved road safety.

Table 11 - KPIs for smart convoys

KPI	Requirement or Values
Unambiguous Range	500 – 2000 m
Unambiguous Velocity	50 m/s
Range Resolution	0.5 m
Velocity Resolution	0.05 m/s
Angle Resolution	Azimuth: 2 deg, Elevation: N/A
Angle Accuracy	Azimuth: 1 deg, Elevation: N/A
Range Accuracy	0.1 m
Velocity Accuracy	0.5 m/s
Miss-Detection	5 %
False Alarm	5 %
PHY Signal Processing Latency	0.5 s
Application Layer Latency	N/A
Update Rate	1 time per second
Availability	90 % – 95 %

KVIs

This use case KVIs, showcased in Table 12, are centred around improving safety via coordinated driving, aiming to reduce human error. Security is strengthened via closed-network data sharing, while privacy is protected by ensuring that sensitive data, such as position and speed, is securely transmitted and stored. Trustworthiness is essential for reliable, real-time convoy control. Environmentally, smart convoys reduce CO₂ emissions by optimising speeds and minimising traffic disruptions. Economically, affordability ensures accessibility and business value through improved fuel efficiency and reduced operational costs.

Table 12 - KVIs for smart convoys

Societal	
KVI 1: Safety	X
KVI 2: Security	X
KVI 4: Privacy	X
KVI 5: Trustworthiness	X
Environmental	
KVI 6: Reduction of CO2 emissions	X
Economical	
KVI 8: Affordability	X
KVI 9: Business value	X

6.2 Detection, positioning, localisation of unconnected objects

6.2.1 Use case: Intruder detection on secure areas

6.2.1.1 Objectives

The goal is to use the sensing capabilities of the network infrastructure for intruder detection capabilities around secure areas, contributing significantly to public safety and security. This feature paired with motion detectors, and cameras, will boost the prevention of unauthorized access and suspicious activities within the coverage of the sensing network.

6.2.1.2 Description

The detection of intruders into sensitive areas is important to ensure that persons and assets inside private zones are protected. Nowadays, various security technologies are available, including CCTV surveillance and infrared motion detectors. Nevertheless, these solutions come with certain limitations, such as restricted coverage, and visibility or blind spots in the case of surveillance systems, and susceptibility to weather conditions in the case of infrared motion detectors. Besides, for wider areas, the installation and maintain of those technologies might be expensive. On the contrary, radio signals enable the monitoring of locations for various visibility and weather conditions, covering wider areas, and reducing the need to install new infrastructure.

The wireless network is set up to protect a secure area within specific time frames. During this period, to ensure privacy considerations, the APs utilise the transmitted radio signals for communications and to detect if a potential intruder breaks the restricted perimeter. The received radio signals are analysed by the network and upon detecting an intruder, the network triggers alerts in real-time. The alerts can be sent to the client and public or private security agencies. By integrating security personnel, clients, and the wireless network, the sensing technology facilitates agile information sharing and effective response.

6.2.1.3 Requirement's analysis (KPIs/KVIs)

KPIs

For intruder detection use cases, radar-related KPIs, showcased in Table 13, are essential to enable precise and reliable real-time detection of intruders. These KPIs guarantee accurate object detection, which is critical in both indoor and outdoor environments where intruders can enter. Low error rates, in terms of missed detections and false alarms, are vital for maintaining trust in the detection system's reliability. Finally, minimised latency and regular data updates are crucial for real-time responsiveness, supporting timely interventions from the public/private protection services.

Table 13 - KPIs for intruder detection on secure areas

KPI	Requirement or Values
Unambiguous Range	300 m
Unambiguous Velocity	5 m/s
Range Resolution	0.1 m
Velocity Resolution	0.05 m/s
Angle Resolution	N/A
Angle Accuracy	N/A
Range Accuracy	0.5 m
Velocity Accuracy	0.1 m/s
Miss-Detection	2 %
False Alarm	2 %
PHY- latency	2 s
Application-related Latency (ex. Identification of objects)	N/A
Update Rate	0.5 times per second
Availability	95 % – 99 %

KVIs

The KVIs for this use case, showcased in Table 14, address societal, environmental, and economic aspects. Societal KVIs emphasise safety and trustworthiness, ensuring user confidence and protection. Environmental KVI focuses on the reduction of CO₂ emissions, promoting sustainability. Economically, the indicators include affordability and business value, highlighting the importance of cost-effectiveness and operational efficiency. These KVIs establish a comprehensive framework that balances social responsibility, environmental stewardship, and economic viability.

Table 14 - KVIs for intruder detection in secure areas

Societal	
KVI 1: Safety	x
KVI 2: Security	N/A
KVI 4: Privacy	N/A
KVI 5: Trustworthiness	x
Environmental	
KVI 6: Reduction of CO ₂ emissions	x
Economical	
KVI 8: Affordability	x
KVI 9: Business value	x

6.2.2 Use case: Identification of faults on roads

6.2.2.1 Objectives

Leveraging the sensing capability within wireless network infrastructure to identify road faults. The idea is to exploit the received radio waves through advanced sensing processing to detect various faults, such as potholes, cracks, and uneven surfaces. By providing detailed information about road conditions, the sensing functionality within the wireless network aims to facilitate timely maintenance and improve road safety.

6.2.2.2 Description

Identifying faults, such as potholes, cracks, and surface irregularities, is important for ensuring road safety, a significance heightened when considering potential increases in legal speed limits. Traditional methods of road inspection often rely on manual surveys, which are time-consuming, costly, and prone to human error. Therefore, leveraging the sensing capabilities of the wireless infrastructure for the timely identification of faults on roads emerges as an innovative technology to enhance traffic safety.

The wireless network is configured to monitor road conditions in real-time, which is achieved through the sensing capabilities within the infrastructure, particularly the roadside APs. The APs receive reflected radio waves that contain valuable data concerning road conditions. This information undergoes advanced signal processing, enabling the detection of anomalies such as cracks, potholes, or indications of wear and tear. The system alerts the responsible concessionary in real time if any anomaly is detected on the road surface. Therefore, the concessionary can prioritise and optimise maintenance efforts, allocate resources efficiently, and implement timely repairs. Also, depending on the harshness of the detected anomaly, the wireless network can update GPS navigation systems in real time about the presence of dangerous anomalies.

6.2.2.3 Requirement's analysis (KPIs/KVIs)

KPIs

The KPIs for this use case, showcased in Table 15, are designed to ensure precise and reliable detection of road faults. The defined unambiguous range ensures the system can monitor road conditions over long distances, making it capable of covering rural areas, where the density of APs is lower. Range and angle resolutions guarantee that the system can differentiate closely spaced faults. Low PHY signal processing and application layer latencies are not essential; however, the defined set ensures fast responsiveness for timely reporting of faults.

Table 15 - KPIs for identification of faults on roads

KPI	Requirement or Values
Unambiguous Range	1000 m
Unambiguous Velocity	N/A
Range Resolution	0.5 m
Velocity Resolution	N/A
Angle Resolution	Azimuth: 0.5 deg, Elevation: N/A
Range Accuracy	0.5 m
Velocity Accuracy	N/A
Angle Accuracy	1 deg
Miss-Detection	2 %
False Alarm	5 %
PHY Signal Processing Latency	100 ms
Application Layer Latency	1 s
Update Rate	5 Hz
Availability	90%

KVIs

Safety is the most critical KVI for this use case, as the system aims to enhance road safety and prevent accidents. Reducing CO2 emissions is also important since roads properly maintained improve traffic flow, reducing fuel consumption. Business value results from optimizing maintenance efforts, which reduces costs. Additionally, since the system may use communication users' signals, Security and

Privacy are crucial to protecting user data. Finally, Trustworthiness guarantees that maintenance authorities can rely on the system for accurate fault detection. All these KVIs are showcased in Table 16.

Table 16 - KVIs for identification of faults on roads

Societal	
KVI 1: Safety	x
KVI 2: Security	x
KVI 4: Privacy	x
KVI 5: Trustworthiness	x
Environmental	
KVI 6: Reduction of CO2 emissions	x
Economical	
KVI 8: Affordability	N/A
KVI 9: Business value	x

6.2.3 Use case: Intrusion detection of UAVs

6.2.3.1 Objectives

The objective to detect intentional or non-intentional intrusion of unwanted UAVs in zones where potential danger can exist. The goal is to complement existing or future detection and countermeasure systems with early detection of UAV intrusion and cooperation with other detection systems. The cases may include low-altitude UAVs, which can hardly be monitored and managed, or intrusion of non-cooperative UAVs (Unmanned Aerial Vehicles) in unwanted zones like airports, cities, military bases, electrical plants, etc.

6.2.3.2 Description

The timely detection of such intrusion will become increasingly crucial as the development of UAVs for many missions is increasing exponentially. Traditional systems include Radio Direction Finders (RDF) and usual radar installations. However, RDF requires radio communication from the UAV and may be less efficient in the case of non-cooperative UAVs. The system may be inoperant in some cases of low altitude UAVs and operate system may be inoperant in some wireless network will complement these detections means. They will be particularly efficient in urban areas where the wireless network is deployed with many cells/access points.

2 main situations can be identified:

- Situations where the potential intrusion is well identified like no-fly zones in airports, military bases or some plants. In that case the type of intrusions is well identified, and the wireless network can be focused on detecting these specific illegal UAV flights.
- Situations where many types of UAV can exist and where the intrusions are legal or not. In that case, each situation must probably be identified, and for each situation, the wireless network would cooperate with an application-oriented detection and countermeasure system.

6.2.3.3 Requirement's analysis (KPIs/KVIs)

KPIs

For the intrusion detection of UAVs use case, the unambiguous range is designed to cover sufficient area for low-altitude UAVs, while the velocity and angle resolutions ensure accurate tracking of UAV movements. The range and velocity accuracies allow for precise positioning and identification of intruding UAVs. Low miss-detection and false alarm rates ensure reliability, minimising undetected intrusions and unnecessary alerts. Low latency values are critical for real-time detection and rapid response, while the update rate and availability ensure continuous and reliable monitoring. All these KPIs are showcased in Table 17.

Table 17 - KPIs for intrusion detection of UAVs

KPI	Requirement or Values
Unambiguous Range	300 m
Unambiguous Velocity	30 m/s
Range Resolution	0.1 m
Velocity Resolution	0.2 m/s
Angle Resolution	Azimuth: 0.1 deg Elevation: 0.1 deg
Range Accuracy	0.05 m
Velocity Accuracy	0.05 m/s
Angle Accuracy	Azimuth: 0.1 deg Elevation: 0.1 deg
Miss-Detection	1 %
False Alarm	5 %
PHY Signal Processing Latency	10 ms
Application Layer Latency	1 s
Update Rate	50 Hz
Availability	98 %

KVIs

For this use case, the key KVIs, showcased in Table 18, include safety, security, privacy, trustworthiness, and business value. Safety is essential, as the network aims to prevent accidents by detecting UAVs in specified zones. Security ensures the integrity of the system by the sensitive user data. Trustworthiness guarantees that the system provides reliable, accurate detections. Finally, business value is a consequence of the reduction of costly surveillance methods.

Table 18 - KVIs for intrusion detection of UAVs

Societal	
KVI 1: Safety	x
KVI 2: Security	x
KVI 4: Privacy	X
KVI 5: Trustworthiness	x
Environmental	
KVI 6: Reduction of CO2 emissions	N/A
Economical	
KVI 8: Affordability	N/A
KVI 9: Business value	x

6.2.4 Use case: Identification of intrusion on railways

6.2.4.1 Objectives

To devise a system to identify intrusions on railway tracks accurately through the sensing capabilities

of the wireless network infrastructure. The goal is to enhance railway safety by swiftly identifying unauthorised access to railway tracks. The prompt identification of intrusions, including the entry of people, animals, or objects onto railways, will minimise accidents and disruptions to train services.

6.2.4.2 Description

Detecting intrusions along railways is crucial for enhancing railway security and preventing service interruptions and accidents. One conventional approach to identifying intrusions is through video surveillance. However, deploying the required infrastructure is costly and relies on human monitoring of real-time video, which may lead to human error. An innovative approach to intrusion detection involves leveraging the existing wireless network infrastructure along railways. By processing radio waves, the wireless network infrastructure detects unauthorised access and potential intrusions along railway tracks with reduced costs.

The sensing capability is enabled within the existing wireless network infrastructure along railway corridors, namely APs and relays. These elements exploit the transmission and reflection of radio waves to capture data indicative of railway activity and any deviations thereof. Through sophisticated signal processing algorithms, anomalies such as trespassing, unauthorised entry, or suspicious behaviour are swiftly identified. Upon detection of anomalous patterns or unauthorised presence, immediate alerts are triggered, swiftly notifying railway authorities and relevant stakeholders.

6.2.4.3 Requirement's analysis (KPIs/KVIs)

KPIs

The unambiguous range was set based on the typical distance between track-side APs in railways to identify intrusion in railway use cases. Since the system focuses on detection, the velocity-related KPIs are acceptable enough to detect moving objects such as people or animals. In addition, miss-detection and false alarm rates are kept low to ensure the system reliably identifies actual intrusions while avoiding unnecessary alerts. Meanwhile, PHY signal processing and application layer latencies are defined to deliver near real-time responses. Finally, availability is a crucial KPI for this use case, ensuring it operates with high reliability and consistency under various conditions. All these KPIs are showcased in Table 19.

Table 19 - KPIs for identification of intrusion on railways

KPI	Requirement or Values
Unambiguous Range	500 m
Unambiguous Velocity	10 m/s
Range Resolution	20 cm
Velocity Resolution	1 m/s
Angle Resolution	Azimuth: 1 deg Elevation: 1 deg
Range Accuracy	10 cm
Velocity Accuracy	1 m/s
Angle Accuracy	Azimuth: 0.5 deg Elevation: 0.5 deg
Miss-Detection	1 %
False Alarm	3 %
PHY Signal Processing Latency	100 ms
Application Layer Latency	1s
Update Rate	5 Hz
Availability	99 %

KVIs

For this use case, the key KVIs, showcased in Table 20, are safety, security, privacy, trustworthiness, and business value. Safety guarantees protection by detecting unauthorised access to railway tracks, while security and privacy ensure user data integrity. In addition, trustworthiness is related to the generation of reliable and accurate alerts, and business value focuses on cost savings and operational efficiency by replacing costly surveillance methods with a more effective method.

Table 20 - KVIs for identification of intrusion on railways

Societal	
KVI 1: Safety	x
KVI 2: Security	x
KVI 4: Privacy	x
KVI 5: Trustworthiness	x
Environmental	
KVI 6: Reduction of CO2 emissions	N/A
Economical	
KVI 8: Affordability	N/A
KVI 9: Business value	x

6.3 Environmental monitoring

6.3.1 Use case: Weather monitoring in smart cities

6.3.1.1 Objectives

The objective is implementing a weather monitoring system adapted for a specific geographic region, such as urban or metropolitan areas, but providing enhanced resolution. It generates detailed and precise weather data at a localised level within these regions, enabling more accurate forecasting and targeted decision-making for urban planning, emergency management, and citizen safety. Enhancing weather forecasting and response by using the wireless network infrastructure improves the accuracy and timeliness of weather forecasts, allowing city officials and citizens to promptly respond to severe weather conditions, thereby enhancing public safety and disaster preparedness. Reusing the network infrastructure for sensing purposes related to weather monitoring systems provides also cost savings benefits for covering the urban city area managed.

6.3.1.2 Description

The frequency of localised weather events like microbursts, and flash floods has increased due to climate change in recent years, which combined with the densification of urban areas has led to elevated risks. Therefore, the monitoring of those phenomena within urban areas is crucial for preventing loss of life and significant property damage in the future. However, traditional weather monitoring systems are typically designed to cover large geographic areas with low spatial and temporal resolution, presenting challenges in accurately detecting and monitoring localised weather events within cities and responding promptly. In contrast, utilising the radio signals of a wireless network for weather monitoring transforms the network into an extensive weather sensor network. This approach has the potential to accurately identify the formation of such events in highly localised areas and issue real-time weather alerts to individuals and relevant institutions within those areas.

The sensing capacities make the wireless network infrastructure operate as a weather sensor. The communication signal transmitted by the APs is used to collect weather data. The received radio signals, containing valuable meteorological information, are then analysed by the network in real-

time. When significant fluctuations of weather parameters like wind speed/direction or temperature are detected, the network promptly triggers alerts. These alerts are transmitted to locals, authorities, and emergency management agencies.

Moreover, this use case enhances cost efficiency by utilising existing infrastructure, reducing the need for additional investments in weather monitoring equipment.

Through the integration of weather monitoring capabilities into the existing wireless network infrastructure, the system facilitates rapid information sharing, leading to effective response strategies to mitigate the impact of adverse weather conditions on city operations and citizen safety. Moreover, the weather monitoring system can be integrated with other smart city infrastructures, such as traffic management and public health systems, allows for a holistic approach to urban management.

6.3.1.3 Requirement's analysis (KPIs/KVIs)

KPIs

For weather monitoring use cases, radar-related KPIs, showcased in Table 21, are essential to enable reliable weather changes monitoring. These KPIs guarantee accurate imaging of antennas surroundings, which are critical in complex outdoor environments.

Table 21 - KPIs for weather monitoring in smart cities

KPI	Requirement or Values
Unambiguous Range	150 m
Unambiguous Velocity	10 m/s
Range Resolution	1 m
Velocity Resolution	0.05 m/s
Angle Resolution	N/A
Angle Accuracy	N/A
Range Accuracy	1 m
Velocity Accuracy	0.5 m/s
Miss-Detection	10 %
False Alarm	10 %
PHY- latency	2 s
Application-related Latency (ex. Identification of objects)	N/A
Update Rate	0.5 times per second
Availability	95 % – 99 %

KVIs

The KVIs for this use case, showcased in Table 22, address environmental and economic aspects. Environmental KVI focuses on reducing CO₂ emissions related to using dedicated devices for weather monitoring, promoting sustainability. Economically, the indicators include affordability and business value, highlighting the importance of cost-effectiveness and operational efficiency.

Table 22 - KVIs for weather monitoring in smart cities

Societal	
KVI 1: Safety	N/A

KVI 2: Security	N/A
KVI 4: Privacy	N/A
KVI 5: Trustworthiness	N/A
Environmental	
KVI 6: Reduction of CO2 emissions	x
Economical	
KVI 8: Affordability	x
KVI 9: Business value	x

6.4 Smart home

Potential applications: presence, proximity, fall, intrusion detection

6.4.1 Use case: Fall detection

6.4.1.1 Objectives

The fall detection target system in smart homes will focus on providing immediate emergency responses by detecting falls quickly and communicating them to emergency services or caregivers. This rapid response is crucial in reducing the severity of potential injuries. Continuous monitoring of residents through environmental and wearable sensors aims to proactively identify fall risks, while the integration with healthcare systems ensures that incident data is promptly shared with medical providers to facilitate informed and effective medical responses.

6.4.1.2 Description

In this application, the macro 6G cellular network, along with potential indoor-coverage radio unit will be used to detect falls. In this approach, the infrastructure will continuously monitor the resident's movements to detect patterns indicative of a fall. Upon detecting a fall, the system will instantly alert predefined emergency contacts or services, providing them with the exact location within the home and relevant data on the incident. Integration with medical systems and IoT health tracking devices will allow for the immediate relay of crucial health data, enabling emergency responders to prepare appropriate medical interventions prior to arrival.

6.4.1.3 Requirement's analysis (KPIs/KVIs)

KPIs

For fall detection use cases, the set of KPIs showcased in Table 23 guarantees the accurate detection of falls, focusing on accurate range, velocity, and angle measurements. For example, low miss-detection and false alarm rates are crucial to ensure reliability and minimise unnecessary warnings to emergency services, respectively. Also, low latency and high update rates are required to guarantee real-time warnings, minimising the response time of emergency services. Finally, the availability requirement ensures the system remains operational with minimal downtime, providing continuous safety monitoring.

Table 23 - KPIs for fall detection

KPI	Requirement or Values
Unambiguous Range	50 m
Unambiguous Velocity	10 m/s
Range Resolution	0.1 m
Velocity Resolution	0.1 m/s
Angle Resolution	Azimuth: 2 deg Elevation: 1 deg

Range Accuracy	0.2 m
Velocity Accuracy	0.1 m/s
Angle Accuracy	Azimuth: 1 deg Elevation: 1 deg
Miss-Detection	2 %
False Alarm	5 %
PHY Signal Processing Latency	0.1 s
Application Layer Latency	2 s
Update Rate	5 Hz
Availability	98 %

KVIs

The KVIs for this use case, showcased in Table 24, address mainly societal and economic aspects. Societal KVIs highlight the importance of accurately detecting fall incidents while protecting the transmitted data against unauthorised access and ensuring compliance with privacy regulations. Economical KVIs concentrate on cost-effective solutions for widespread adoption in smart homes, making advanced safety accessible.

Table 24 - KVIs for fall detection

Societal	
KVI 1: Safety	x
KVI 2: Security	x
KVI 4: Privacy	x
KVI 5: Trustworthiness	x
Environmental	
KVI 6: Reduction of CO2 emissions	N/A
Economical	
KVI 8: Affordability	x
KVI 9: Business value	N/A

6.4.2 Use case: Gesture Recognition for Controlling Smart Home Devices

6.4.2.1 Objectives

The objective of the gesture recognition system in smart homes is to provide intuitive and hands-free control of various smart devices, enhancing user convenience and accessibility. By recognising specific hand gestures, users can seamlessly interact with their smart home environment, controlling lighting, media playback, temperature, and other devices without the need for physical buttons or remote controls.

6.4.2.2 Description

The radio signals received by indoor 6G radio units are used for gesture recognition. This functionality detects and interprets body movements made by residents within the smart home. The system continuously monitors for recognisable gestures, such as waving, swiping, or pointing, using indoor radio units of the 6G network positioned strategically throughout the home.

The radio waves received by indoor radio units are processed for gesture recognition. Upon detecting a relevant gesture, the system interprets the gesture and triggers corresponding actions on connected devices. For example, waving a hand could turn on/off lights, and swiping gestures could adjust

volume or temperature settings. Integrating gesture recognition technology with smart home devices enables a gesture-controlled home, enhancing user experience and accessibility, especially for persons with mobility limitations or disabilities.

6.4.2.3 Requirement's analysis (KPIs/KVIs)

KPIs

For the gesture recognition use case, the KPIs in Table 25 ensure that the system operates with high accuracy and responsiveness, which are necessary to deliver a pleasing user experience. The range, resolution, and latency parameters are adjusted to effectively detect various gestures within typical indoor environments. Low miss-detection and false alarm rates are vital for reliable operation, minimising user frustration. High update rates and availability further ensure real-time performance and system reliability.

Table 25 - KPIs for gesture recognition for controlling smart home devices

KPI	Requirement or Values
Unambiguous Range	10 m
Unambiguous Velocity	5 m/s
Range Resolution	0.05 m
Velocity Resolution	0.01 m/s
Angle Resolution	Azimuth: 5 deg, Elevation: 5deg
Range Accuracy	0.1 m
Velocity Accuracy	0.05 m/s
Angle Accuracy	Azimuth: 5 deg, Elevation: 5 deg
Miss-Detection	5 %
False Alarm	10 %
PHY Signal Processing Latency	10 ms
Application Layer Latency	50 ms
Update Rate	30 Hz
Availability	95 %

KVIs

The selected KVIs, in Table 26, guarantee that the gesture recognition system delivers a secure, reliable, and user-centric experience. Security and privacy are vital to protecting user data and preventing unauthorized access. Trustworthiness is important to providing accurate gesture recognition-based applications within smart homes. Finally, business value ensures the solution aligns with industry goals by enhancing the appeal and integration of smart home technologies.

Table 26 - KVIs for gesture recognition for controlling smart home devices

Societal	
KVI 1: Safety	N/A
KVI 2: Security	x
KVI 4: Privacy	x
KVI 5: Trustworthiness	x
Environmental	
KVI 6: Reduction of CO2 emissions	N/A
Economical	
KVI 8: Affordability	N/A

KVI 9: Business value	x
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7 Interworking methodology with the other Work Packages

This chapter offers a brief overview of the interactions between WP2, the technical development packages (WP3-5) and the implementation phase package (WP6).

7.1 WP2 Relation to Design WPs (3-5)

WP2, "Use Cases, Requirements, Architecture, and Sustainability", establishes the technical and architectural groundwork for the project. It is fundamental in defining use cases and system requirements that guide the development in WPs 3 through 5. This WP aims for a unified approach, ensuring the project's technical objectives align with sustainable and practical implementation strategies. As WP3 and WP4 have been identified as very interrelated this deliverable also outlines steps to ensure an efficient and synergetic collaboration between the two WPs.

7.1.1 WP3-4 Interworking

7.1.1.1 Introduction

Workpackages 3 (WP3) and 4 (WP4) represent two of the core research WPs in 6G-MUSICAL. While each WP addresses distinct objectives, they are highly interrelated, making their collaboration essential for the project's success. To maximize the potential of both WPs, the following considerations must be emphasized:

1. **Mutual Awareness of Research Progress:** Establishing mechanisms for continuous exchange of information and updates is crucial. Regular meetings and shared documentation can help maintain awareness of ongoing research activities, results, and insights in both WPs. This awareness enables both WPs to align their strategies.
2. **Uniformity of Notation and Frameworks:** Standardizing the notations, terminologies, and frameworks used across WP3 and WP4 will help a mutual understanding while ensuring a broader impact. This uniformity improves the communication, ensures compatibility of outputs, and will facilitate the integration of findings from both work packages into the broader 6G-MUSICAL initiative.
3. **Synergies in Research:** Close interaction between WP3 and WP4 is critical to leverage complementary expertise, avoid duplication of efforts, and identify opportunities for joint innovation.

By ensuring a high degree of interaction and collaboration between WP3 and WP4, the project can achieve a unified approach that may advance the objectives of 6G-MUSICAL and result in a broader impact.

7.1.1.2 Review of WP3 & WP4 objectives

According to the Description of Work (DoW), the objectives of the two WPs are:

Workpackage 3:

1. Investigate and define waveforms suitable for both communication and radio-sensing
2. Investigate and define precoding and receiver techniques for joint radar and communication networks.
3. Investigate and define compression techniques to exploit the fact that in radio-sensing the number of targets is significantly below the time-frequency degrees of freedom.
4. Investigate and define compression techniques for the fronthaul.

Workpackage 4:

1. Investigate and define network synchronisation mechanisms that enable multi-node radio sensing with high accuracy and resolution.
2. Investigate and define multi-node joint processing algorithms for radio –sensing and positioning.
3. Investigate and define efficient resource allocation algorithms for radio-sensing and positioning in the context of cell-free.

While both WP3 and WP4 aim to advance the integration of communication and radio-sensing in 6G networks, their scopes are distinct yet complementary. WP3 primarily focuses mainly on the **link-level aspects**, such as waveform design, compression techniques, and joint radar-communication processing at the individual link level. In contrast, WP4 addresses **multi-node aspects**, including network synchronization, joint multi-node processing, and efficient resource allocation across a distributed system. This distinction emphasizes that WP3 lays the groundwork for enabling robust link-level functionalities, while WP4 extends these principles to the network level, incorporating synchronization and multi-node collaborative processing to achieve high accuracy and resolution in complex radio-sensing environments.

7.1.1.3 Main points of intersection

Though the WPs have different objectives they are interrelated and the intersection is particularly evident in the following areas:

- **Joint Radar and Communication Processing:** WP3 investigates in Task 3.2 techniques for precoding and receiving signals that are suitable for both communication and radio sensing. These efforts align closely with WP4's focus on developing multi-node joint processing algorithms in Tasks 4.1 and 4.3 where the link-level strategies and algorithms will be reused and enhanced to be utilized in multi-node processing either distributed or centralized.
- **Compression and Fronthaul Efficiency:** WP3's work on compression techniques (Task 3.3) for radio sensing and fronthaul directly supports WP4's objectives in Task 4.3 by ensuring that the network-level processing can handle large-scale data efficiently. without compromising accuracy.
- **Harmonizing Objectives:** WP3 and WP4 both contribute to the overarching goal of achieving seamless integration between communication and sensing in 6G networks. While WP3 focuses on optimizing the building blocks, WP4 ensures these blocks function cohesively across distributed nodes in a synchronized and resource-efficient manner.

By fostering close collaboration between WP3 and WP4, the project can ensure that innovations at the link level are seamlessly translated and scaled to the network level, creating a unified and high-performance system for 6G communication and sensing.

7.1.1.4 Steps taken to reinforce integration of WP3 and WP4

To strengthen collaboration between WP3 and WP4, a meeting was held to define key steps for fostering a productive and synergetic partnership. The collaborative process will evolve as deliverables are developed in both work packages, ensuring that their outputs are aligned and mutually beneficial. Several decisions and actions have been agreed upon to facilitate this interaction:

- **Participation in Monthly Progress Meetings:** The WP3 leader (UCL) will invite WP4 partners to attend WP3 monthly progress meetings, fostering a continuous exchange of ideas and

updates. Similarly, WP4 will invite WP3 partners to participate in its monthly meetings to ensure ongoing alignment and integration.

- **Mutual Presentations:** Members from WP3 and WP4 will present their work in each other's meetings whenever a topic is identified as having potential cross-workpackage implications. This will encourage knowledge sharing, identify opportunities for joint contributions, and align methodologies where appropriate.
- **Strategic Agenda Setting in Global Meetings:** The technical manager and project coordinator will include specific agenda points in global project meetings to discuss topics identified as convergent between WP3 and WP4. These discussions will ensure a regular review of interdependencies leading to the definition of actionable steps to enhance synergy and collaboration.

Potential additional forms of collaboration can be envisioned, facilitated by the fact that many partners are active in both WP3 and WP4. Particularly during the development of the first WP3-WP4 deliverables, it is expected that sharing of information and discussion will identify overlaps or gaps that will be addressed to ensure a seamless and effective collaboration

By fostering these collaborative efforts, WP3 and WP4 can significantly enhance the quality, efficiency, and impact of their work, ultimately driving the project's success.

7.2 WP2-5 relation to implementation WP6

WP6, "Integration and Validation", is designed to validate the technology developed in the project's design WPs within a laboratory setting. The outputs from WP3-WP5 provide the essential components for creating focused testbeds in WP6. These testbeds are crucial for conducting experiments that offer PoCs for the key technologies developed, directly stemming from the enabling technologies outlined and initiated in WP2.

8 Conclusions

The objective of this deliverable was to provide essential data to enable technical WPs 3-6 to progress coherently towards the unified goal described in the Description of Work (DoW). To achieve this, the deliverable has been structured using a top-down approach. Starting from the global vision outlined in the DoW, we progressively refined our focus: first, by identifying the key parameters and indicators that will define the feasibility, performance, and sustainability of the technology under research, and then by assigning specific values to these parameters and indicators.

The use cases identified and described in this document represent services currently recognised in research and literature as promising candidates that will benefit from the integration of communications and radio sensing. These use cases are highlighted in anticipation of standardisation, with the understanding that novel services may emerge as the technology evolves. From these use cases, the service requirements necessary for global deployment have been derived, leading to the identification of the main technological KPIs needed for WPs 3-6 and the classification of the KVis to be addressed in Task 2.4.

These KPIs are divided into two categories: conceptual KPIs and demonstration KPIs. Conceptual KPIs outline the requirements that 6G nodes must meet to support future 6G services, while demonstration KPIs focus on the specific targets to be achieved in the planned Proofs of Concept (PoCs). This distinction is crucial because the PoCs are limited in scope and address specific aspects of the use cases. To demonstrate these aspects, we may employ a scaling approach. For example, by establishing a relationship between radio resources in the PoCs, we can assure that augmenting a given resource will improve the related KPI in a well-understood and predictable manner.

Additionally, the document addresses KVis, which, although more intangible than KPIs, are crucial for mass-market technologies. KVis ensure that technologies adhere to economic, environmental and societal sustainability goals. The main outcome of this document is the classification of KVis, providing a framework that will be further developed in Task 2.4.

In conclusion, the current findings highlighted in the document, together with the classifications and numerical values, provide a solid foundation for the initial work of WPs 3-6 in both optical and wireless domains. These values will dictate the objectives and activities performed within the project. Additionally, the awareness of the required types of KVis, which are transversal across different WPs, ensures that all aspects are considered holistically.

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